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D2.1 Decentralised Orchestrator Early Release

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Abbreviations

Term	Meaning
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
QoS	Quality of Service
NFS	Network File System
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
SLO	Service Level Objective
SLA	Service Level Agreement
DSL	Domain-Specific Language
EMS	Event Management System
API	Application Programming Interface
CEP	Complex Event Processing
EPM	Event Processing Manager
EPA	Event Processing Agent
EPN	Event Processing Network

Term	Meaning
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IoT	Internet of Things
FOA	Fog Orchestrator Agent
FO	Fog Orchestrator
CN	Cloud Nodes
FN	Fog Node
OS	Orchestrator Space
OC	Orchestrator Client
SDO	Service-Defined Orchestrator
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
SOTA	State of the Art
VM	Virtual Machine
AWS	Amazon Web Services
MAPE-K	Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute over Shared Knowledge
RA	Resource Agent
SA	Swarm Agent
LR	Lead Resource
MA	Monitoring Agent
DCEP	Distributed Complex Event Processing
SSH	Secure SHell
CNCF	Cloud Native Computer Foundation
HA	High Availability
MPLS	Multi Protocol Label Switching
ROS	Robot Operating System

Term	Meaning
AMS	Adaptive Monitoring Service
RV	Regressor Variables
DV	Dependent Variables
AMQP	Advanced Message Queueing Protocol
EPL	Event Processing Language
DAG	Direct Acyclic Graph
LSTM	Long Short Term Memory
GA	Genetic Algorithms
GCNN	Graph Convolutional Neural Network
ML	Machine Learning
MA-DRL	Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning

Executive Summary

This document reports on the results of the research and technical development activities conducted under Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Swarmchestrate project that aim to empower decentralized, smart, and sustainable application orchestration in a wide range of Cloud-to-Edge settings. This document introduces the key architectural designs and implementation choices on decentralised orchestration, context-aware semantics, adaptive monitoring, and AI-driven energy optimisation.

The deliverable describes the design of a TOSCA-based semantic model that enables rich, machine-interpretable application descriptions. These models capture not only structural and resource requirements, but also contextual dependencies, quality-of-service objectives, and monitoring specifications and constraints which are crucial for informed, autonomous decision-making across heterogeneous infrastructure. From this, the system enables applications to deploy, using a peer-to-peer orchestration layer built from resource agents that collaboratively discover and provision available resources. The deployment of the application, swarm formation, as well as the runtime management along with different types of potential reconfigurations are thoroughly detailed.

Another portion of the work addresses the delivery of a decentralised monitoring framework, the Event Management System (EMS), with a context-aware metric model, which supports both raw and composite metrics, and integrates mechanisms for defining service-level objectives as enforceable constraints. The EMS provides the feedback loop necessary for intelligent orchestration, supporting reconfigurations and self-healing through a decentralised complex event processing system.

In parallel, WP2 introduces the first iteration of Swarmchestrate's energy optimisation framework, which integrates ecological considerations into the orchestration loop. By embedding environmental cost as a first-class concern in resource selection and task allocation, the orchestrator could balance performance and sustainability in real time.

Taken together, these results constitute the first fully integrated release of Swarmchestrate's decentralised orchestrator. The outputs of this work package include an extended TOSCA specification tailored to swarm-based application modelling, a functioning prototype of the orchestration and monitoring subsystems, and a validated approach to energy-aware deployment. These developments establish the architectural and semantic backbone upon which subsequent work packages will build more advanced features in monitoring, optimisation, intelligence and full lifecycle management of application.

1. Introduction

1.1 Document Purpose

This document presents an in-depth overview of the research and development conducted within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the Swarmchestrator project. WP2 is dedicated to enabling decentralised, self-adaptive orchestration of applications across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum, building on prior work to realise a scalable and intelligent orchestration space. At its core, this work package addresses the technical challenges of managing distributed applications in highly dynamic and heterogeneous environments. The focus is on developing the models, mechanisms, and tools needed to support context-aware application specification, automated deployment, decentralised monitoring, intelligent runtime management, and energy-aware orchestration.

Through the integration of AI-driven decision-making, distributed systems principles, and context-awareness, WP2 lays the groundwork for resilient and efficient application behaviour across diverse infrastructure layers. By integrating context-awareness, AI, and distributed systems principles, WP2 advances the Swarmchestrator vision of a scalable, flexible, and sustainable orchestration space for modern applications that must operate in heterogeneous and evolving infrastructure environments.

1.2 Document Structure

The structure of this document follows the progression of the tasks defined within WP2, reflecting the logical flow of technical development. It begins with the design and implementation of context-aware semantics for Cloud-to-Edge applications in Section 2, describing how existing standards such as TOSCA have been extended to support decentralised, constraint-driven orchestration in the Swarm-based environment. Building on this foundation, the document explores in Section 3 the mechanisms developed for automated application deployment and run-time management and reconfiguration, showcasing how context-aware descriptions, AI-driven decision-making, and decentralised resource awareness come together to enable intelligent placement of applications across a distributed infrastructure.

The discussion then moves to the development of an adaptive and decentralised monitoring system in Section 4, which will enhance a previously established event-driven framework with capabilities such as self-healing, adaptive sampling/filtering to ensure efficiency in a heterogeneous environment. Next, in Section 5, the document discusses the work on improving the energy performance of cloud-edge systems, which promises lower operating expenses, a smaller carbon footprint and more sustainable digital services, utilising state-of-the-art machine learning technologies. Lastly, Section 6 concludes this document.

2. Design and implementation of context-aware semantics for Cloud-to-Edge applications

This section introduces the primary interface for describing applications, capacities and monitoring metrics in Swarmchestrator.

In section 2.1, we introduce a generic language for describing applications in the cloud, named TOSCA. Then, Section 2.2 looks at how we use this language to describe applications and capacities in Swarmchestrator. Finally, Section 2.3 describes the approach to model monitoring metrics with TOSCA.

2.1 Introduction about TOSCA

The Open OASIS standard TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) will provide the primary interface to the Swarmchestrator ecosystem. It will be used to describe applications, resources (capacities), monitoring and quality of service (QoS) requirements. TOSCA specifies a generic language for vendor-free descriptions of the components that comprise an application running in the Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

Key features of TOSCA include *nodes*, *capabilities* and *requirements* to describe software and infrastructure, *relationships* to describe interconnections between these components, and *interfaces* and *policies* to describe the run-time behaviour of these components. All of these descriptions are added to a TOSCA Service Template that is interpreted by a TOSCA orchestrator to realise the deployment. TOSCA authors can define types for these features, historically inheriting from a set of *normative* types. The rich type system in TOSCA supports simpler Service Templates, and enables the reusability and portability in component descriptions.

TOSCA is expressed in YAML¹, which is a data serialisation language and superset of JSON, intended to be more human readable than JSON itself. See Figure 1 for a basic “Hello World” example in TOSCA. This example defines a generic web application, which requires some specific compute to host it.

```
service_template:
  node_templates:
    my-application:
      type: WebApplication
      requirements:
        - host:
            node: Compute
            allocation:
              num-cpu: 2
              mem-size: 128 MB
```

¹ <https://yaml.org/>

Figure 1: Hello World in TOSCA

For an application in Swarmchestrator, *nodes* are used to describe the microservices, cloud VM instances and edge nodes that comprise a swarm, with *relationships* determining where specific microservices will be executed. It is envisaged that TOSCA *policies* will eventually be used to describe monitoring and QoS requirements too, targeting specific services or resources that they apply to.

In late 2024, the TOSCA Technical Committee approved TOSCA version 2.0 as a Committee Specification. The release of version 2.0 marked a major change in the specification, bringing with it more flexibility for domain-specific applications of TOSCA. A leading feature of TOSCA v2.0 was replacing *normative* types with *profiles*, which empower TOSCA authors to write more relevant type definitions for their domain areas. A significant work in Swarmchestrator is to create a profile for the domain area of swarm computing, which is, to our knowledge, the first such effort in the TOSCA community.

2.2 TOSCA for Application and Capacity Description

The following subsections introduce the Swarmchestrator approach to describing the application, capacity, and monitoring aspects of the project.

2.2.1 Application

The application description in TOSCA aims to fully describe all the details of the application that are required for successful deployment. Several broad sections of this representation have been identified. These include a metadata section, component specification, resource requirements, and quality of service goals. These sections are also discussed in section 3.3.1, but are described here from the perspective of TOSCA. All fields that have been identified to date are listed in Table 1.

<i>Section</i>	<i>Attributes</i>
METADATA	
Information	Name, Author, Creation date, Version, Classification
COMPONENT SPECIFICATION	
Application	Image, command, arguments, environment variables, resources (min required cpu/ram), limits (max allowed cpu/ram)

Relationships	Volumes (NFS, emptyDir, configMap, hostPath), other containers, nodeSelector.
Behaviour	Type (Deployment, Job, DaemonSet); strategy (recreate, rolling update); replicas; restartPolicy; cron schedule
Security	Secrets, credentials, keys
RESOURCE REQUIREMENTS	
Specification	Instance type, Num CPU, Mem RAM, Num GPU, Disk size, Network bandwidth, Num of instances, Energy type, Security configuration, Price

Table 1: Application TOSCA fields

The **metadata section** includes fields useful for search, storage, filtering, and versioning, such as *name*, *author*, *creation date*, *version*, and *classification*. TOSCA supports top-level metadata fields that support adding this information to service templates. An example can be seen in the representative TOSCA template in Figure 2.

The **component specification section** includes all the details that are necessary to ensure the correct deployment of the application microservices. These include the common parameters that can be set to configure an OCI-compliant application container, such as *container image*, *command*, *arguments*, *environment variables*, and *resource limits*. These are currently defined as TOSCA properties, as seen in the example in Figure 1. Also, this section includes the relationships with *volumes*, *cloud or edge resources*, and other *containers*, which can be defined using TOSCA requirements. Specific behaviours and security can be defined using TOSCA interfaces, which include *strategies* for deployment, *policies* for restarting containers, the number of *replicas* to deploy, or *secrets*, *credentials*, and *keys*. These features are undergoing development (so are not shown in Figure 1).

```
1  tosca_definitions_version: tosca_2_0
2
3  metadata:
4    name: tosca-in-swarmchestrate
5    author: UoW
6    version: 0.0.1
7    created: 31/5/2025
8    classification: examples
9
10 description: >-
11   Sample application representation in Swamrchestrate.
12
13 service_template:
14   node_templates:
15     my-microservice:
16       type: Container.OCI
17       properties:
18         image: uowcpc/testing:latest
19         cmd: sleep 60
20       requirements:
21         - host: my-cloud-vm
22
23     my-cloud-vm:
24       type: Compute.EC2
25       capabilities:
26         num_cpu: 2
27         mem_size: 2 GB
```

Figure 2: Example application TOSCA in Swarmchestrate

Figure 2 also shows an example of **resource requirements**, which define the cloud or edge infrastructure that is needed to host the application microservices. This section defines capabilities such as the *number of CPUs* (**num_cpu** in the example), *memory size* (**mem_size** in the example), *disk size*, *number of instances*, and many others. These are defined using TOSCA capabilities and properties, as seen in the figure.

The final section of the application representation is the **quality of service goals** section. This section defines aspects that support the desired run-time orchestration of the application such as *performance targets*, *provider preferences*, *placement requirements*, and *budget constraints*. These will be defined using TOSCA policies and are currently undergoing development.

To support application owners in building their application representations, Swarmchestrate proposes to collect the key details of the application deployment in a simpler, JSON structure, eventually using these values to generate a TOSCA Service Template, as in the example above. A similar approach was applied successfully in a previous project², where application deployment details were captured as simple key-value pairs that are used to generate deployment descriptors to be executed by an orchestrator.

² <https://github.com/UoW-CPC/ADTGenerator>

2.2.2 Capacity

Capacity descriptions in TOSCA aim to catalogue the available resources that are available in Swarmchestrator. These will be authored by capacity providers to define the cloud or edge resources that they make available for applications in Swarmchestrator.

Capacity representations have a **metadata** section, much like application representations do. The key section of a capacity representation is the **resource specification**, detailing the available *resource types* and *quotas*, their *costs* and *locations*, supported *operating systems* and *architectures*, and *energy-related* information. Edge devices have further specifications, which may include *available sensors*, specific *hardware* or *software* details, and information on *security*, *trust* and *access*.

A new feature of TOSCA v2.0 has been identified to support the Swarmchestrator approach to capacity representations. The *capability allocation* feature is intended to set a predefined amount of resources available for a given TOSCA node. In Swarmchestrator, in case a capacity is limited, its definition can specify a fixed allocation. When applications are deployed to Swarmchestrator and all the resources that they require are provisioned, the *capability allocation* on the respective capacity will decrease accordingly. When an application terminates and resources are released, the *capability allocation* of those resources will increase. Capacity representations in Swarmchestrator are currently being finalised, and this feature, among others, is currently being investigated for implementation.

2.3 Metric Model for QoS Monitoring in TOSCA

2.3.1 Introduction

The Event Monitoring System (EMS) that is responsible for monitoring the different applications and their microservices running in different Swarmchestrator's swarms requires a well-defined input in order to function efficiently. This input is called the Metric Model. It is based on a technology-agnostic modelling framework, CAMEL DSL [1], which has been translated to TOSCA according to the requirements of the project. In the metric model, there is a concise but detailed description of the monitoring requirements and the System Level Objectives (SLOs) that should not be violated. The metric model is constructed upon the idea that different components of a distributedly running application may need different QoS requirements. For this reason, different components of the Metric Model are grouped according to their type or a logical grouping of their types (scopes). The two main entities of the Metric Model are the Metrics and the Requirements.

Metrics are the entities whose values represent a monitoring aspect of a property. They can be divided into two categories. Raw metrics are the unprocessed values of the monitoring attributes of a system, collected directly from the resources/microservices (infrastructure-level metrics) through sensors or received from exposed endpoints of the applications (application-level metrics). Composite metrics require additional processing,

e.g. mathematical operations, to create more complex metrics, often combining multiple components or measurements together throughout specific time intervals.

Requirements are constraints specified by the owners of the applications of the Swarmchestrator universes that define the desired conditions of operation of their microservices. These are applied on the metrics that have been requested to be monitored, and can be specified either per application component, scope or on an application level. These are essentially the Service Level Objectives (SLOs), whose values must either be under specified thresholds (demonstrating normal application behavior), when exceeded (demonstrating an undesired behavior resulting) alerts are created by the monitoring system for an initiation of the reconfiguration of the system.

2.3.2 Development Process

In order to define the entities needed we used the TOSCA standard language, and followed the example of the MICADO³ project as well as previous work on example TOSCA entities for monitoring applications[2]. The following entities were defined after working and experimenting with the Puccini framework, which is a Cloud topology management and deployment toolset. It allowed us to parse TOSCA and to make sure that we abide to the rules of the language.

During the development process, we have been in continuous contact with the UOW, who has been in constant communication with the TOSCA main developers. Through meetings and discussions with them, we received valuable feedback on our work. In the following subsections, the current version of the TOSCA definition of monitoring is presented.

2.3.3 Node Types

In the node types category, we defined the MonitoringComponent node type, which will be the entity responsible for the monitoring of applications. It is derived from `tosca:Root`, and it possesses two kinds of capabilities: The MetricMonitor capability and the SloMonitor capability, which will be explained in detail in the following section.

³ <https://www.micadoproject.eu/>

```

MonitoringComponent:
  description: >-
    The MonitoringCollector node type is used to define an EMS that will collect
    monitoring metrics from EMS nodes.
  derived_from: tosca:Root
  capabilities:
    metrics:
      type: MetricMonitor
      description: >-
        The metrics that the monitoring collector will collect.
    requirements:
      type: SloMonitor
      description: >-
        The SLOs that the monitoring collector will monitor.

```

Figure 2: Definition of MonitoringComponent node type

The second node type we defined is the MonitoringScope. It was used to define a clustering of components that need to be monitored by the EMS. It includes a list of components of MonitoringComponent node type.

```

MonitoringScope:
  description: >-
    The MonitoringScope node type is used to define a greater clustering of
    components that will be monitored by the EMS.
  derived_from: tosca:Root
  properties:
    components:
      type: list
      required: true
      description: >-
        The components that will be monitored by the EMS.
    entry_schema:
      type: string
  capabilities:
    metrics:
      type: MetricMonitor
      description: >-
        The scope-wide metrics that the monitoring collectors will collect.
    requirements:
      type: SloMonitor
      description: >-
        The scope-wide SLOs that the monitoring collectors will monitor.

```

Figure 3: Definition of MonitoringScope node type

2.3.4 Capabilities

Two main capabilities were defined in the TOSCA for monitoring that reflect the functionalities of the Monitoring Component node type: the MetricMonitor Capability and the SloMonitor Capability.

The MetricMonitor capability provides monitoring capabilities for the MonitoringComponents. It allows two kinds of metrics: raw and composite ones, each belonging to a different type. The raw metrics belong to the rawMetric data type, and the composite to the compositeMetric. (Each data type will be discussed in the next section.) Both are part of the capability type, and their attributes are expected as a list, but are not both required. Its definition used by the Puccini parser can be seen below:

```
MetricMonitor:
  description: >-
    The Monitor capability allows to define the metric monitoring capabilities of an
    EMS component.
  properties:
    raw:
      type: list
      required: false
      entry_schema:
        type: rawMetric
    composite:
      type: list
      required: false
      entry_schema:
        type: compositeMetric
```

Figure 4: Definition of MetricMonitor capability type

The SloMonitor capability provides the MonitoringComponents the capability to define the Quality of Service (QoS) requirements set by the owners of the applications. They can be defined as a threshold set on a metric that abides to the System Level Objectives (SLOs). A list of SLO constraints is expected to be of data type sloConstraint. More about this particular data type will be discussed in the next section. The definition used by the Puccini parser can be seen below:

```
SloMonitor:
  description: >-
    The SloMonitor capability allows to define the SLO monitoring capabilities of an
    EMS node.
  properties:
    slo:
      type: list
      required: false
      entry_schema:
        type: sloConstraint
```

Figure 5: Definition of SloMonitor capability type

2.3.5 Data Types

In TOSCA, we defined three different data types. Two types for the different metrics categories: `rawMetric`, `compositeMetric`, and one for the QoS requirements definitions: the `sloConstraint`.

Raw Metric

The `rawMetric` data type defines the structure for describing a raw monitoring metric that can be collected by the Event Monitoring System (EMS). It is used by monitoring components to specify low-level metrics along with the necessary information required for their collection. Each raw metric must include a name identifying the metric (e.g. `cpu_util`), a sensor that indicates the monitoring probe (e.g. `Netdata`), and a `collection_frequency`, which determines how often the metric is going to be forwarded for processing. The `collection_output` specifies the amount of data that is going to be forwarded during the time interval. For example, all data collected in the particular interval can be forwarded, the first or the last ones, respectively. Optionally, a config property allows additional configuration parameters to be passed to the metric collector. One important config parameter is the collection interval, which defines how often the metrics are collected by the sensor. If this is omitted, the metrics will be collected according to the `collection_frequency` parameter defined above. This data type enables the EMS to flexibly configure and manage diverse monitoring inputs. The TOSCA definition for this entity is shown below.

```

rawMetric:
  description: >-
    The rawMetric data type is used to define a raw monitoring metric
    that can be used to collect monitoring data with EMS.
  properties:
    name:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The name of the metric that will be collected.
    sensor:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The sensor that will be used to collect the metric.
    config:
      type: map
      required: false
      description: >-
        Extra configuration for the metric collection.
    collection_frequency:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The frequency of the metric collection.
    collection_output:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The output of the metric collection.

```

Figure 6: Definition of RawMetric data type

Composite Metric

The compositeMetric data type allows monitoring components within the EMS to define high-level metrics derived from existing raw or composite metrics. These metrics are calculated based on a specified formula, which references other defined metrics within the EMS profile. Each composite metric must include a name, a collection_frequency that determines the interval at which the metric is evaluated, and a collection_output that defines whether the result reflects the first, last, or all values within the evaluation window. To support temporal analysis, the metric also specifies a window_type (e.g., sliding, batch, etc.) and a window_size, both of which control how data is aggregated over time. Optionally, a grouping can be defined to scope the metric calculation across different dimensions such as per host, zone, region, or even across swarms. This structured definition supports complex monitoring use cases through metric composition and temporal windowing. The TOSCA definition used by the Puccini⁴ parser is shown below:

⁴ <https://puccini.cloud/>

```

compositeMetric:
  description: >-
    The compositeMetric data type is used to define a composite monitoring metric
    that can be used to collect monitoring data with EMS.
  properties:
    name:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The name of the metric that will be collected.
    formula:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The formula used to calculate the composite metric. The contained metric
        should be defined in the rest of the EMS profile. It could be either a raw
        or a composite metric.
    collection_frequency:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The frequency of the metric collection. Should be an integer followed
        by a time unit. E.g. 15 s.
    collection_output:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The output of the metric collection. Should be either first, last or all.
    window_type:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The type of the window used for the metric calculation. E.g. sliding.
    window_size:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The size of the window used for the metric calculation. Should be an integer
        followed by a time unit. E.g. 15 s.
    grouping:
      type: string
      required: false
      description: >-
        The grouping of the metric calculation. Should be either per_host, per_zone,
        per_region or cross_swarms.

```

Figure 7: Definition of CompositeMetric data type

SLO Constraint

The `sloConstraint` data type defines a Service Level Objective (SLO) that can be enforced within the EMS monitoring framework. It enables application owners to specify Quality of Service (QoS) goals by setting conditions over a defined metric. Each SLO constraint includes a name for identification, a metric, which refers to either a raw or composite metric previously defined in the EMS profile, and a threshold value that represents the acceptable performance limit. The operator field determines how the metric is evaluated against the threshold, supporting standard comparison operators such as `>`, `<`, `>=`, `<=`, `==`, and `!=`. This structure allows EMS to continuously evaluate whether monitored metrics adhere to the expected QoS targets. The formal TOSCA definition of this data type is provided below:

```

sloConstraint:
  description: >-
    The sloConstraint data type is used to define a Service Level Objective constraint
    that can be used to define SLOs with EMS.
  properties:
    name:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The name of the SLO constraint.
    metric:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The name of the metric that the SLO will monitor. Must be defined in the rest
        of the EMS profile.
    threshold:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The threshold of the SLO. Should be a number.
    operator:
      type: string
      required: true
      description: >-
        The operator of the SLO. Should be one of the following: >, <, >=, <=, ==, !=.

```

Figure 8: Definition of sloConstraint data type

Next Steps

As for now, grouping of metrics across different components for further processing is being handled by node type: MonitoringScope. However, there may be more effective mechanisms in TOSCA for such work. TOSCA categories that we would like to further investigate are Groups and Policies defined in the TOSCA 2.0 manual [3] to potentially better handle metrics of different components and replace the MonitoringScope node type. Furthermore, we would like to refactor the data types, and potentially create an extra, more generic type for all metrics from which raw and composite metrics will derive, for cleaner and better code structure. Along with those changes, improvements and adaptations to the translator of TOSCA of the monitoring system will take place.

3. Application orchestration in the Cloud-to-Edge continuum

The Cloud-to-Edge continuum represents a dynamic ecosystem where computational resources are distributed across multiple administrative domains, ranging from centralised data centres to localised edge nodes, each with unique computational capabilities, constraints, and performance characteristics [4]. The rapid increase in such paradigms has transformed how modern distributed applications provision, manage and utilise

computational resources. Orchestration solutions are typically employed to deal with the associated challenges of managing complex distributed applications in the Cloud-to-Edge compute continuum, including their deployment on heterogeneous computing resources and run-time operations [5], [6], [7].

The challenges include ensuring seamless and simultaneous access to the heterogeneous and decentralised resource landscape, along with effective coordination across diverse cloud, fog, and edge providers to enable end-to-end services. Additionally, achieving optimisation of multiple, often conflicting quality of service (QoS) goals—such as optimal placement, resource usage efficiency, application performance, cost, energy consumption, and security—remains a critical focus. Scalability of the continuum, adaptability to changing application and infrastructure conditions, and efficient monitoring to collect workload and resource usage statistics throughout the spectrum are also essential requirements.

In this section, we will discuss the overall approach of Swarmchestrator as a distributed orchestrator for applications in the Cloud-to-Edge. Swarmchestrator is designed to address the aforementioned challenges by embracing a decentralised, application-centric model that distributes orchestration logic across multiple nodes in the continuum. Instead of relying on a centralised control plane, Swarmchestrator empowers applications to autonomously manage their life cycle through lightweight, composable agents embedded within their execution environment. More specifically, Section 3.1 presents a thorough investigation of the existing landscape of orchestration solutions, followed by an overview of the foundational concepts that underpin the Swarmchestrator system in Section 3.2. Section 3.3 then delves into the design and implementation of the application deployment phase, detailing how applications are provisioned and initialised across distributed resources. Finally, Section 3.3 outlines the proposed design for runtime management, focusing on how the system maintains application performance, adapts to dynamic conditions, and ensures ongoing compliance with QoS goals.

3.1 State of the art

The orchestration landscape is highly diverse, with distinct subsets differing significantly. To simplify this, we classify solutions into two categories: low level and high level. Lower-level solutions are middleware that lacks high-level abstractions and requires manual, low-level configuration. They don't support core orchestration functions like automated deployment or dynamic reconfiguration but provide essential foundations for higher-level orchestration solutions. Higher-level solutions use high-level interfaces (e.g., GUIs, TOSCA) to abstract resource management, often building on lower-level ones. They target application owners, while lower-level solutions serve orchestrator developers.

3.1.1 Low-level solutions

In recent years, several vendor-agnostic middleware solutions have emerged to support resource and application management across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. While they help higher-level orchestrators extend to the edge, they often lack key features like high-level abstractions and dynamic, user-driven orchestration. This section reviews some of these initiatives.

EVE [8], a Linux Foundation (LF) project, enables scalable centralised management of large volumes of edge compute nodes, where the orchestration of the underlying hardware and installed software is achieved through the open EVE API. EVE is complementary to other LF frameworks, including Open Horizon [9], EdgeX Foundry [10], and Fledge [11]. Open Horizon facilitates the management and deployment of workloads on edge devices from a management hub cluster. EdgeX Foundry provides an edge IoT plug-and-play ecosystem with an aim to simplify and standardise edge computing architectures in the industrial IoT market. Lastly, Fledge is a Kubernetes-compatible container orchestrator for edge devices.

KubeEdge [12] is an open-source project that extends Kubernetes orchestration to edge nodes by integrating them into a central cluster. It enables developers to manage applications and devices at the edge like in the cloud. However, its centralised model risks edge isolation, making workload management impossible if the Kubernetes master is unreachable. Kubefed [13] and Submariner [14] use a federated approach that lets edge sites operate independently during network partitions, avoiding a single control point.

StarlingX [15], like KubeEdge, extends container orchestration to the edge but differs by being OpenStack-specific and forming independent edge clouds rather than connecting nodes to a central cluster. It uses a central Kubernetes-based control center with multiple edge sub-clouds, creating a federated architecture similar to Kubefed and Submariner. However, it lacks cross-cloud orchestration, as each sub-cloud is managed independently.

OpenIoTfog [16] targets industrial IoT by extending orchestration to edge devices and supporting Industry 4.0 functions like real-time data aggregation, predictive maintenance, and Digital Twins. It enables programmable logic controllers that can be updated without downtime. Functionally similar to KubeEdge, OpenIoTfog uses an agent on edge devices to integrate them into a centralised cluster for dynamic service deployment and to collect, standardise, and securely communicate sensor data via industrial protocols. Lastly, Fornax [17] is an edge computing framework that manages resources using a hierarchical, multi-layer tree structure. This allows infrastructure management across multiple layers (N layers), unlike the two-layer models of KubeEdge and OpenIoTfog or the federated approaches of Kubefed, Submariner, and StarlingX.

3.1.2 High-level solutions

High-level solutions are further classified as Concept only (academic proposals), Research project based initiatives, and industry initiatives. The following subsections review and analyse representative solutions from each category.

Concept only

Many academic papers address Cloud-to-Edge orchestration. The remainder of this section discusses a representative set of these papers.

ENORM [18] is a framework for managing edge node resources and workload deployment. It employs a decentralised architecture where each edge node handles its own resource decisions, though the system remains static since all nodes are predefined to cloud managers. ENORM primarily focuses on edge operations such as provisioning, monitoring,

vertical scaling, and application offloading, while details about cloud server management are not specified. Fernandez et al.[19] proposed a slice orchestrator that automates IoT service orchestration based on operational or business needs across shared infrastructures. It creates network slices, configures edge and cloud tenants, and deploys IoT functions based on resource requirements. The architecture is hybrid in nature, where a central orchestrator manages slices, and domain-specific orchestrators are responsible for resource selection and deployment in their respective domains.

Alam et al. [20] proposed a three-layer reference architecture using Docker to automate microservice deployment specifically focusing on publish–subscribe based IoT applications. The system adopts a centralised model, with monitoring, adaptation, and orchestration handled in the cloud. The fog layer acts as a gateway between cloud and edge, supporting tasks like device status updates and data transformation.

Santos et al.[21] address optimal application placement in smart city environments, aiming to reduce bandwidth usage and improve latency. Their solution extends the ETSI NFV MANO [22] architecture with monitoring and data analysis features. It adopts a hybrid model: a central cloud node (CN) handles global coordination, SLA monitoring, and data analysis, while fog nodes (FNs) manage local infrastructure, devices, and microservice lifecycles autonomously, including resource discovery, monitoring, and policy enforcement. Similarly, Foggy [23] also focuses on minimising latency and optimising application placement, using a centralised model with an orchestration server (OS) for decision-making and clients (OC) on each node for enforcement. Foggy, however, includes several unique features such as integration with version control and CI tools, a pluggable policy-based deployment planner, and a JSON-based container specification using qualitative terms (e.g., Low, Medium, High).

Mathias et al. [24] proposed a centralised Fog Orchestrator (FO) for service management, global monitoring, and orchestration, supported by Fog Orchestrator Agents (FOAs) on fog nodes handling edge device management, monitoring, and security. The FO dynamically composes TOSCA-based templates for deployment and runtime control using data from resource catalogues and monitoring tools. Unlike other approaches, FOAs can take over FO duties if connectivity is lost, though this fallback role must be predefined. The solution focuses solely on non-cloud layers.

Hetero-Edge [25], like the approach by Mathias et al. [24], uses a centralised orchestrator for non-cloud (edge) layers. Tailored for computer vision applications, it leverages Apache Storm (or similar frameworks) to decompose applications into tasks represented as a directed acyclic graph. A custom scheduler maps these tasks to edge nodes, aiming to minimise end-to-end latency based on estimated performance and resource needs. A similar model is proposed by Donassolo et al. [26], focusing on cost-efficient provisioning of IoT applications at the edge.

Castellano et al. [27] proposed a distributed model where a new Service-Defined Orchestrator (SDO) instance is launched for each application deployment. Each SDO relies on declarative statements describing component topology, system state, objectives, and event-action rules to guide orchestration decisions. To handle resource contention among

multiple SDOs shared resources are partitioned, and components may be terminated if allocations fail. HYDRA [28] adopts a decentralised architecture forming a peer-to-peer overlay where each node acts as both orchestrator and compute resource. It supports location-agnostic and location-aware deployments, focusing on scalability and resilience through dynamic partitioning, with each orchestrator independently managing a specific application. Similarly, Caravela [29] also uses a P2P-based architecture for resource discovery and scheduling, however adopts a market-oriented model, where volunteer edge resources can join dynamically, and are rewarded for participation. However, unlike HYDRA, Caravela excludes cloud-layer provisioning.

Other notable contributions include GeneSIS [30], which uses a model-driven approach to automate deployment of various artefacts (e.g., binaries, ThingML [31], containers); ECCO [32], which enables coordinated edge–cloud orchestration for road context assessment; KubeHICE [33], which tackles hardware heterogeneity by matching containerised applications to compatible devices based on ISA; and fuzzy logic-based solutions by Gand et al. [34] and Sonmez et al. [35], which address deployment under uncertainty in cloud–edge environments.

Beyond the core orchestration solutions, some works have explored related but complementary aspects. For instance, [36] focuses on trusted orchestration, aiming to track orchestration activities to enhance trust among system actors. Kochovski et al. [37] proposed a smart contract-based architecture for SLA enforcement in decentralised environments. More recent efforts use deep reinforcement learning for dynamic load balancing [38] and network clustering [39] to optimise cloud–edge systems.

Research project-based initiatives

In recent years, several EU-funded projects have developed Cloud-to-Edge solutions. This section reviews such efforts.

SODALITE@RT [40] enables application deployment and management across Cloud-to-Edge infrastructures using TOSCA models and Infrastructure as Code (IaC). It follows a centralised approach with a meta-orchestrator that consumes TOSCA models and provider-specific Ansible scripts from an IaC repository. While this allows custom deployments, it places additional burden on developers compared to other TOSCA-only solutions [7], [41]. Edge resources are managed as part of a Kubernetes cluster, but the process for forming this cluster is unclear. SODALITE@RT also includes an event-condition-action policy language, access control, and secure storage for secrets, though it lacks support for application-level security settings.

Capillary [42] uses a custom monitoring system to support QoS-aware offloading across resource layers based on user-defined parameters, such as geographic location. It follows a centralised architecture with a Capillary container orchestrator that handles deployment and offloading. Offloading follows a layer-by-layer model (e.g., edge to fog to cloud), inspired by capillary flow. The system takes a TOSCA-based deployment model as input, including service requirements, zones, and QoS thresholds. At runtime, violations trigger alarms that prompt the orchestrator to update the TOSCA model and redeploy services. While cloud

resources are dynamically provisioned, provisioning of fog and edge resources is not detailed.

MiCADO-Edge [7] is a centralised framework that automates deployment and management of microservice applications across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum using a single TOSCA-based model. This model includes resource details, topology, placement, scaling policies, and security settings. A key feature is its ability to integrate non-cloud (fog/edge) resources into a central cluster before deployment, allowing developers to reference them in the model. MiCADO-Edge supports custom dynamic scaling policies but lacks support for context-aware placement, requiring static service-to-resource mappings.

PrEstoCloud [43], [44] extends TOSCA-based orchestration with an optimisation step. It starts with a high-level TOSCA model containing abstract components and optimisation goals, which is then transformed into a concrete instance-level model with specific resource mappings for deployment. This enables optimised service placement. Additionally, it supports predictive reconfiguration by adapting to changing data stream conditions, targeting data-intensive applications.

mF2C [45] proposed a decentralised N-layered architecture spanning edge (Layer-N) to cloud (Layer-0), unlike the 2-layer or 3-layer models in MiCADO-Edge [7] and Capillary [42]. Their proposed solution is decentralised, where deployed mF2C agents collaborate to find nearby resources for service execution. A service request, expressed in JSON with resource requirements, is first handled by lower-layer agents; if unmet, it is escalated to higher layers. The system supports automatic agent discovery, dynamic clustering, and reconfiguration for mobility. However, it lacks features like scaling, offloading, dynamic provisioning, and customisable policies.

DECENTER [46] targets smart and safe construction sites with solutions tailored to construction-specific challenges. Its standout feature is a Blockchain-based resource brokerage system that enables trusted, auditable, and verifiable resource negotiation. It adopts a centralised architecture with four main components: Application Composer, QoS-aware Decision Maker, Monitoring System, and Orchestrator. Users define services and QoS goals via a GUI, and deployment decisions are made based on monitoring data. DECENTER also supports automatic redeployment on QoS violations but lacks dynamic auto-scaling and offloading capabilities.

Pledger [47] also makes use of Blockchain to improve trust, secure communication and to enable ad-hoc networks between the resources of non-cloud layers to collaborate with each other for the execution of a specific application. Although Pledger's overall architecture follows a centralised model, its implementation does not comply with a traditional adapter-based interaction model between different parts of the system. Pledger provides different toolkits for resource providers to integrate their resources into the Pledger ecosystem and for the application owners to perform mapping of their applications on specific resources, which is further assessed and reconfigured by the core Pledger service to ensure optimised use.

Rainbow [48] addresses fog-specific service constraints using a high-level abstraction where applications and their constraints are defined as a graph. This input guides the decentralised orchestration system in service placement and execution. The orchestration system follows a decentralised model, where the different components run across participating nodes and communicate via a publish-subscribe model, with an Orchestrator Repository maintaining system state. Rainbow supports dynamic edge device registration and reconfiguration based on SLO violations but does not handle cloud resource provisioning.

Slack4Things [49] is an OpenStack-based framework designed to manage IoT devices seamlessly, abstracting their location, network, and technology specifics. This work was later extended by Merlini et al. [50] into a distributed orchestration framework spanning cloud, fog, and edge layers. It supports both horizontal offloading (task migration within the same layer) and vertical offloading (across layers, e.g., edge to fog). The system uses independent managers at each layer, enabling full or partial application deployment directly to any tier.

Besides the projects above, several new EU research efforts have been launched under the European Cloud, Edge and IoT (CEI) Continuum initiative [51], which aims to foster a dynamic, open ecosystem for Cloud-Edge-IoT technologies. Notable projects within CEI include AerOS, FluidOS, ICOS, NebulOus, NEMO, and NEPHELE. Similarly, the AI-enabled Computing Continuum from Cloud to Edge (CognitiveCloud) cluster [52] features related projects like AC3, ACES, CloudSkin, CODECO, COGNIFOG, DECICE, EDGELESS, MLSysOps, and SovereignEdge.Cognit.

Industry initiatives

This section reviews industry platforms that support combined cloud-edge orchestration. These were selected based on available implementations and technical documentation or white papers. Although often built on open-source tools like Docker and Kubernetes, these vendor-specific solutions mainly target (5G) network service orchestration. As industry products, their documentation typically highlights features for customers rather than technical details, making it difficult to evaluate. Still, they are included here for completeness, though no detailed comparison table is provided.

HPE GreenLake [53] is an infrastructure-as-a-service solution that extends the public cloud model to private clouds, multi-cloud, and on-premises environments, offering agile cloud services everywhere. It provides a centralised interface to integrate, manage, and monitor diverse resources, including bare-metal, compute, storage, containers, data protection, HPC, AI/ML, and virtual desktops.

Intel Smart Edge Open [54] is an edge computing toolkit that extends cloud-native tech for heterogeneous edge environments, from on-premises to regional data centers. Built on Kubernetes, it offers modular “experience kits” combining 5G and cloud-native components to simplify complex network deployments and cut development time. Key features include resource management for hardware/software monitoring and telemetry for real-time insights that support efficient scheduling.

AMCOP [55] is an open-source platform for orchestrating and managing cloud-native network services and edge applications. It offers intent-based orchestration and real-time,

policy-driven closed-loop automation for edge and 5G service assurance. AMCOP integrates with existing OSS/BSS systems (northbound) and orchestrates infrastructure across multiple heterogeneous Kubernetes clusters (southbound).

Ormuco [56] is a platform designed to enable decentralised edge computing for efficient data processing. Its Cerebro virtual sysadmin collects logs from diverse nodes and applications to learn normal behaviour and alert owners of potential anomalies.

Azion [57] is an end-to-end encrypted edge orchestration service with cloud management and zero-touch provisioning for large-scale edge networks. It enables real-time resource control and service orchestration via an agent on edge nodes that securely connects to the cloud-based Real-Time Manager. The platform allows device management and custom service creation through its Edge Node and Edge Services modules.

ONAP [58] is a vendor-agnostic platform offering policy-driven service design, analytics, and lifecycle management for large-scale workloads. It enables network operators to orchestrate physical and virtual network functions, leveraging existing infrastructure within a global VNF ecosystem. The Kubernetes-based ONAP Operations Manager (OOM) handles end-to-end lifecycle management, monitoring, scalability, and resiliency.

ZEDEDA [59] is a cloud-based orchestration platform for secure remote management of distributed edge hardware and applications across cloud and on-premises environments. It uses EVE-OS, an open, vendor-neutral OS from the Linux Foundation's LF Edge, which simplifies deployment, orchestration, and security of cloud-native and legacy apps. EVE-OS supports VMs, containers, and Kubernetes, ensuring data encryption and device integrity.

3.2 Concepts

The following are some of the important foundational concepts related to the Swarmchestrate project.

3.2.1 Swarmchestrate in a nutshell

The core idea behind the Swarmchestrate project is to develop a distributed orchestration system that intelligently manages the deployment and runtime operations of microservice-based applications across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. At its foundation, Swarmchestrate functions as a middleware platform (Figure 9) that accepts application specifications, along with their associated quality of service (QoS) goals, constraints, and preferences, and autonomously deploys them by identifying and allocating the most suitable and cost-effective resources. Unlike provider-centric orchestrators that prioritise infrastructure utilisation or profit, Swarmchestrate adopts an application-centric perspective, focusing on optimising outcomes for application owners. This includes minimising deployment costs, satisfying performance requirements, and adapting to dynamic conditions. Upon deployment, the selected set of resources collectively forms a logical swarm that hosts and supports the application. Each application is thus conceptualised as a self-contained swarm, wherein distributed components collaborate and manage themselves using principles of swarm intelligence, enabling self-organisation,

decentralised decision-making, and adaptive reconfiguration to continually meet the QoS objectives.

Figure 9: Swarmchestrator Middleware

3.2.2 Resource

In the Swarmchestrator project, a resource refers to any computational entity—physical or virtual—that can be directly managed by the Swarmchestrator system. This encompasses a broad spectrum of devices across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum, including dynamically provisioned virtual machines in cloud data centres, physical edge or fog nodes, and even intelligent sensors equipped with processing capabilities. Examples of such resources include cloud-based VMs, edge gateways, S3-compatible storage units, or embedded IoT devices. Each resource is described by a set of contextual attributes, such as hardware specifications, supported operating systems, geographic location, mobility, battery level, and network connectivity. These contextual characteristics are essential for determining the resource’s suitability for hosting specific application components, enabling Swarmchestrator to make informed, context-aware decisions about deployment and runtime management.

3.2.3 Resource provider

A resource provider refers to the entity that owns or manages the infrastructure on which computational resources operate. In the context of cloud resources, this typically refers to cloud service providers such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, or Google Cloud, which offer virtual machines, storage, and other services. In the case of edge environments, the resource provider may be the owner or operator of physical edge devices, such as local enterprises, telecom operators, or individual users, who contribute their hardware to host application components.

3.2.4 Capacity

A capacity in the Swarmchestrator ecosystem refers to a logical grouping of resources made available by an entity, known as a capacity provider. This abstraction allows diverse and heterogeneous resources, potentially spanning multiple locations and resource providers, to be managed and accessed as unified, coherent units. For example, the Acme Corporation may own four edge devices in London, maintain access to 100 CPUs and 512 GB of memory on AWS, and also utilise 48 CPUs and 1024 GB of memory on Microsoft Azure. While these resources originate from different underlying resource providers, Acme can expose them as one or more capacities within Swarmchestrator, according to its operational goals or organisational structure. As a capacity provider, Acme is responsible for managing the availability, access policies, and monitoring of the grouped resources, enabling Swarmchestrator to treat them as logically organised building blocks for efficient application deployment and runtime orchestration. The provider of the capacity, e.g. Acme Corporation in the above-mentioned example, will be referred to as the capacity provider.

3.2.5 Users

The users in Swarmchestrator are the application operators, and therefore, we do not deal with the application users. Providing a suitable user interface and support for application users is the responsibility of the application operators and is outside the scope of the Swarmchestrator orchestrator.

3.3 Application deployment in the Swarm-based Orchestration Space

The fundamental responsibilities of an orchestration solution revolve around two key functions: the automated deployment of applications and their efficient runtime management. Building upon these core capabilities, our approach in designing Swarmchestrator intentionally separates the orchestration system into two corresponding phases—deployment and runtime orchestration—to enable modularity, scalability, and adaptability across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. This section begins with an overview of the proposed architecture specifically tailored for distributed application deployment, detailing the mechanisms and workflow involved in coordinating deployment across heterogeneous nodes in Section 3.3.1. Subsequently, Section 3.3.2 presents the current status of our implementation efforts, highlighting the progress made toward realising the Swarmchestrator framework and its capabilities.

3.3.1 Architecture and overall design

Figure 10 shows the Swarmchestrator application deployment process, organised into four key sections. **Application view** allows operators to define their applications using the standardised TOSCA application description format [3]. The **Resource view** comprises a two-layered structure, where *Resources* represent the actual computational resources provided by different cloud and edge providers, e.g. Amazon, Microsoft, Sztaki cloud and

others, and *Capacity* refers to the logical grouping of resources made available by an entity within the Swarmchestrator ecosystem. In Swarmchestrator, every resource is part of a Capacity, which must be registered in the Knowledge Management system to enable discovery and utilisation for application deployment.

The **Knowledge Management** component serves as a distributed knowledge base, handling information related to resource capabilities, their descriptions, system interactions, and decision-making processes. Resources can be discovered based on various contextual attributes and trust factors, facilitating efficient application deployment and dynamic reconfiguration. At the start, **capacities are registered with the knowledge base** through an interface. Registration will be performed using a TOSCA-based resource model. The capacity provider will describe the resources as part of the capacity. The resource description consists of specifications such as processing capability, memory, hardware type, etc., and various required contextual attributes, e.g. usage price per time unit, locality, etc. At the time of registration, the capacity provider will also initiate (set up a new or assign an existing) Resource Agent (discussed later in this section) responsible for providing access to the resources described in the capacity.

Lastly, the **Orchestration Space (OS)** is a decentralised entity operating without central control, functioning as the execution environment for core orchestration functions. The OS is the confluence of three key concepts—Decentralisation, Swarms, and Intelligence—for achieving efficient, optimised, and trusted application orchestration in the Cloud-Edge continuum. Decentralisation stems from the adoption of a distributed architecture, enabling the system to operate without central control. The Swarms, facilitating the execution and management of individual applications as dynamic, cooperative Swarms. Intelligence is embedded through the extensive use of machine learning and optimisation algorithms, driving resource selection and decision-making for reconfigurations. The following subsections break down the OS components in detail.

Figure 10: Architectural view of application deployment

Application

Swarmchestrator is designed to support microservice-based applications, each composed of m loosely coupled components that can be independently deployed and managed across the Cloud-to-Edge continuum. These applications are described using the TOSCA standard, which enables a structured, portable, and machine-readable representation of the application architecture and its orchestration requirements. Within Swarmchestrator, the TOSCA-based application specification captures four key aspects:

1. **Component Specification:** Defines the individual microservice containers that make up the application, including critical configuration details such as environment variables, startup commands, exposed ports, and resource constraints (e.g., CPU and memory limits).
2. **Resource Requirements:** Outlines the specific infrastructure needs for deploying the application, such as preferences for cloud or edge instances, acceptable instance types, minimum and maximum hardware capacities (CPU, RAM, storage).
3. **QoS Goals:** Specifies the application's quality of service objectives, which may include performance targets (e.g., response time, throughput), cost constraints, energy efficiency, data locality or service placement preferences, trust and security requirements, and allowable types or sources of resource providers. These goals guide the orchestrator in making deployment and runtime adaptation decisions that align with the application's operational priorities.
4. **Monitoring Specification:** Defines the custom metrics and performance indicators to be collected and monitored by Swarmchestrator. These metrics are essential for enabling context-aware orchestration, allowing the system to detect deviations from QoS goals and trigger reconfigurations, such as scaling, migration, or reallocation of resources, to ensure continuous compliance throughout the application's lifecycle.

By encapsulating these aspects, Swarmchestrator enables intelligent, flexible, and goal-oriented orchestration of complex microservice applications in highly distributed environments. The TOSCA description is submitted to the OS interface, a network of independent Resource Agents (*Discussed in the next section*) connected through a peer-to-peer (P2P) system.

Resource Agent

The Resource Agent (RA) is a core component of the Swarmchestrator system, designed to perform two primary functions. First, it acts as a representative for one or more Capacities, enabling controlled access to the underlying resources they expose. Second, it plays a critical role in the distributed discovery of suitable resources for application deployment by collaborating with other RAs across the Swarmchestrator ecosystem.

An RA is instantiated when a Capacity Provider registers its resources, along with their contextual attributes such as processing power, memory, hardware type, virtual machine configurations, pricing models, geographical location, and energy efficiency metrics. Once activated, the RA joins a peer-to-peer (P2P) network of other RAs, collectively forming a

decentralised orchestration interface that spans the resource continuum. When a new application is submitted, its specification is introduced to this interface, where one of the RAs in the P2P network takes responsibility for initiating the deployment process. This decentralised approach enables scalable, resilient, and context-aware orchestration, as detailed in the following section.

Overall deployment process

To illustrate the deployment process, we use a simple example involving an application (app1) composed of four microservices, each with distinct resource requirements labeled A, B, C, and D. Upon receiving the application specification (as shown in Figure 11), a Resource Agent (RA-X) is selected to initiate the deployment process. While the selection of RA-X is currently performed randomly, it can be guided by more sophisticated strategies in future implementations, such as load balancing or locality-aware heuristics. Once selected, RA-X coordinates the following steps to identify and allocate suitable resources for deploying the microservices.

1. **Collecting resource offers:** The first step in the deployment process is to identify all potential resource sets that can satisfy the application's requirements—namely A, B, C, and D. As depicted in Figure 11, RA-X initiates this step by broadcasting the application's resource requirements to all other available RAs in the peer-to-peer network, requesting candidate offers. Upon receiving the broadcast, each RA evaluates its capacity by consulting the Knowledge Management component, which provides information on currently available resources, ongoing allocations, and capability constraints. Based on this assessment, each RA determines the extent to which it can fulfil the application's needs, classifying its coverage as **Full** (able to satisfy all requirements), **Partial** (able to satisfy some requirements), or **Zero** (unable to satisfy any). These RAs then respond to RA-X with their coverage details, enabling RA-X to compile a set of unique combinations of offers that collectively meet the application's deployment requirements.
2. **Resource selection:** In this step, the objective is to select the best offer from the pool of candidate resource combinations identified in the previous stage. The best offer represents the most optimal set of resources that maximises the likelihood of meeting the application's QoS goals. Once this optimal resource set is selected and provisioned, it forms a Swarm—a logical grouping of resources that will collaboratively host and serve the application. The selection process considers the following key inputs:
 - a. The resources collected in the previous step,
 - b. The application's QoS goals as defined in its TOSCA specification,
 - c. Dynamically obtained reliability metrics for each offer, which assess the projected impact of each resource on overall QoS compliance. These metrics include historical failure frequency, availability, performance consistency, resource accuracy, network accessibility, and other operational indicators. The reliability metrics will be obtained from the knowledge management component, discussed in D3.1.

These inputs are processed by an AI or optimisation-based algorithms (discussed in D1.1 in details) to produce a ranked list of offers based on their expected ability to meet the application's goals. The top-ranked offer is selected as the winner, and the resources provided by the participating RAs (e.g., RA-1, RA-2, and RA-3 in Figure 11) are allocated to form the application's Swarm. This ensures that deployment decisions are QoS-aware and sensitive to the dynamic context of the Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

Figure 11: Resource offers collection and ranking

3. **Lead SA deployment:** This step marks the initiation of the Swarm—a coordinated group of resources selected from the optimal offer—and the deployment of the lead Swarm Agent (SA). The SA is a core system component responsible for managing the Swarm's lifecycle and behaviour. Multiple SAs operate within a Swarm, collectively ensuring its resilience and autonomy by handling tasks such as monitoring, self-organisation, and dynamic reconfiguration. The lead SA is the first SA instance launched and is tasked with coordinating the assembly of the entire Swarm (as further detailed in the next paragraph). The "Lead SA Deployment" phase begins with the winning set of RAs. Should any resource of this offer become unavailable—due to an expired offer, resource unavailability, or connectivity issues—the system falls back to the next-best offer in the ranked list. The primary objective at this stage is to establish a cluster across the selected resources, which is orchestrated by RA-X through the following sub-steps:
 - a. Identify Lead Resource (LR): RA-X selects the most appropriate resource to host the lead SA and the Kubernetes control plane. Kubernetes has become the industry-standard platform for container orchestration, surpassing alternatives such as Docker Swarm and OpenShift, and thus forms the foundation of our orchestration layer. The selection of the LR takes into account several criteria, including resource capacity (CPU, storage), available utilisation, resource type (Cloud or Edge), networking capabilities, and the prioritisation scores from the offer selection process. The LR is subject to change during runtime if it becomes unavailable or if a better alternative emerges during reconfiguration.
 - b. Instantiate LR: Once selected, the LR is instantiated—for instance, by provisioning a new cloud instance or activating an idle edge device.

- c. Set Up Kubernetes Control Plane: The Kubernetes control plane is deployed on the LR, providing the necessary coordination and management layer for the containers within the Swarm.
- d. Launch Lead SA: The control plane then initiates the deployment of the lead SA, which begins orchestrating the rest of the Swarm's formation.

Upon completion of these steps, the system reaches the state depicted in Figure 12. Here, the Swarm comprises four distinct resource types from three contributing RAs. At this point, only the Lead Resource (type B from RA-2) is active, hosting both the Kubernetes control plane and the lead SA, which will drive the subsequent phase of the application deployment process.

Figure 12: Lead resource

4. **Application deployment:** In this step, the Lead SA finalises the formation of the Swarm and completes the deployment of the application. The process is driven by several inputs, including the TOSCA-based application specification, the details of the participating Resource Agents (RAs), and any necessary credentials for accessing and provisioning the selected resources. The deployment unfolds through the following four key steps:
 - a. Resource Instantiation and Cluster Integration: In coordination with the contributing RAs, the Lead SA provisions the remaining resources. These resources are then integrated into the cluster initiated by the Lead Resource (LR), establishing a unified space for a particular application.
 - b. High Availability Configuration: To avoid a single point of failure, the Lead SA identifies and provisions one or more additional resources to support a highly available (HA) Kubernetes cluster. The selection of these HA nodes follows the same criteria used for choosing the LR, considering factors such as available capacity, resource type, reliability, and proximity. Once selected, the necessary HA configurations are applied to ensure failover and resilience.
 - c. SA Allocation: For distributed self-organisation, a collection of SAs is required. These agents operate alongside the deployed application components, handling local monitoring and reconfiguration tasks. At this stage, the Lead SA

determines the number of SAs needed and selects appropriate resources within the Swarm to host them.

- d. Deployment: Leveraging the Kubernetes cluster scheduler, the Lead SA deploys the remaining SAs, application microservices, and monitoring agents across the allocated resources, ensuring all components are correctly placed and initialised.

Upon completion of these steps, the system reaches the state illustrated in Figure 13. At this point, all required resources—represented as shaded shapes (two triangles, three plaques, one diamond, and one rectangle)—are fully integrated into a cohesive Swarm. Together, they are actively running the four microservices that comprise app1, enabling distributed, self-managing application execution within the Cloud-to-Edge continuum.

Figure 13: Post-deployment

3.3.2 Implementation

After investigation of the functionalities of the key components, such as Resource Agent and Swarm Agent, significant overlapping between the components has been identified. Moreover, the bottom-to-top implementation of the various functionalities is considered as the most effective approach. Therefore, implementation first focused on the lower-level functionalities based on which Resource Agent and Swarm Agent components will rely on later.

The basic groups of functionalities have been identified as follows:

1. **Communication library:** as a decentralised and distributed subsystem the orchestration systems' components will utilise a communication library to build up links between the components and to exchange messages. The current implementation focuses on a p2p communication library that is currently being implemented utilising existing communication libraries such as Twisted⁵.

⁵ Twisted communication library <https://twisted.org/>

2. **TOSCA handling library:** since the descriptors for applications and resources are TOSCA-based, it is essential to handle the descriptors in an identical way by the key components. As such a library is being developed to cover all the necessary functionalities, for example, extraction or manipulation of various fields in the application or resource descriptions.

3. **Microservice management library:** the creation, update or removal of microservices are also a common functionality for the key components, as it has been described in the above design of the orchestration system. A library is being developed that handles microservices in a uniform way, primarily through the kubernetes interface at a certain endpoint of a k3s⁶ cluster previously built for the swarm.

4. **Resource handling library:** the basic resources such as cloud resources or edge devices must be handled by the Resource Agents. To introduce a higher level abstraction for this functionality a library is being developed for covering the most important functionalities such as instantiation/shutdown of cloud virtual machines, deployment and configuration of kubernetes nodes, either on the virtual machines or on edge devices. This library utilises the open-source OpenTufu system to interact and execute cloud operations such as instantiation/deletion of virtual machines.

5. **Capacity handling library:** for testing purposes this library provides functionalities for handling resource related calculations for a given set of resources assigned to a particular Resource Agent. The library is able to return the available free resources, to assign/allocate or reserve resources and to preserve the actual status of the resources. These functionalities help simplify the implementation of the Resource Agent component.

The previously listed reusable libraries are forming the basic building blocks of the main functionalities for the Resource and Swarm Agent components of the decentralised Orchestration System.

For the implementation of the Resource and Swarm Agents, key procedures have been designed and graphically represented. The following **sequence diagrams** give an insight to the implementation of the components without the aim of covering every piece of procedure that is part of the implementation.

A sequence diagram to initialise the first instance of RA in the network is shown in Figure 14. It details the most important parameters for setting up the network of RAs to realise the Swarmchestrator ecosystem.

⁶ K3s Lightweight Kubernetes, <https://k3s.io/>

Figure 14: Sequence diagram to initialise the network of RAs

A sequence diagram to initialise a new RA instance and join it to the network of RAs is shown in Figure 15. It details the most important parameters for extending the network of RAs as part of the Swarmchestrator system. The RAs exchange identifiers in order to keep an up-to-date list of RAs.

Figure 15: Sequence diagram to realise RA's join to the network of RAs

State transition diagrams of the capacity handled by the RAs are shown in Figure 16. This diagram is the basis for implementing the capacity handling library. The states are Free, Reserved, Assigned and Allocated for the lifecycle of the capacities.

Figure 16: State transition diagram of a capacity handled by an RA

A sequence diagram about how capacities are assigned for the incoming/submitted applications specified in TOSCA is shown in Figure 17. The main focus is on distributing the resource requirements of a particular application, collecting the capacity offers of every RAs and performing the ranking to select the most appropriate offer.

Figure 17: Handling submitted applications in RAs

A sequence diagram about how Lead SA deployment is realised by the RA with the cooperation of Resource Provider is shown in Figure 18. The procedure follows the procedure of selecting capacity for the application. Lead SA deployment requires instantiation of resources (virtual machine) by the Lead Resource Agent, setting up the Kubernetes cluster (K3S) and its control pane and finally launching the Lead SA microservice. In this diagram, the diagram contains the steps of persisting capacity state changes as well to the Knowledge Base (that will provide storage functionality in the Swarmchestrator Ecosystem).

Figure 18: Lead SA deployment

Finally, once the Lead SA component has been deployed, its initial task is to deploy the application as part of the Swarm (see Figure 19). The diagram shows the main steps of the application deployment performed by the Lead SA such as 1) validation of resource acquisition and 2) instantiating the microservices assigned to the different capacities instantiated by the various RAs. As a final step, the High Availability feature of the cluster is also realised.

Figure 19: Application deployment

The sequence diagrams shown above introduce the most important internal procedures being implemented as part of the Resource and Swarm Agents for the deployment phase of an application.

3.4 Dynamic runtime management and reconfiguration of the application

The runtime management component of Swarmchestrator is responsible for ensuring that deployed applications continue to meet their specified Quality of Service (QoS) goals throughout their operational life cycle. Once an application is deployed (Figure 13), the associated Swarm Agents (SAs), with the help of Monitoring system, continuously monitor the system state, resource performance, and application-level metrics as defined in the application's TOSCA description. These monitoring activities are decentralised and context-aware, enabling the system to detect deviations or emerging issues such as performance degradation, increased latency, resource exhaustion, or changes in availability.

The monitoring data is collected through lightweight monitoring agents co-located with application components (as can be seen in Figure 13), which feed into a local decision-making engine embedded in each SA. If a QoS violation is predicted or detected, the system triggers a reconfiguration process. Reconfiguration decisions are made using local and collaborative reasoning among SAs, taking into account the up-to-date system metrics, historical reliability data, and the application's original goals. At this stage, we envision several possible reconfiguration actions, including migrating microservices to more suitable nodes, scaling components up or down, adjusting resource allocations, or deploying replicas to address failures or performance fluctuations.

Swarmchestrator's runtime management is inherently adaptive and application-centric—it prioritises the goals of the application owner rather than the interests of infrastructure providers. By adopting principles from swarm intelligence, including decentralised coordination and autonomous local decision-making, Swarmchestrator maintains robust, self-organising behaviour that supports long-term application stability, efficiency, and compliance with diverse QoS constraints. The rest of the section discusses more specific details about the high-level flow, reconfiguration actions, and protocol of how the actions will be realised.

Figure 13 depicts the state of the system when the deployment of an application is completed. From this time onward, the system regarding this specific application will be executed as follows:

1. **Monitoring Agents (MAs)** will continuously observe the state of their respective resources and application components, collecting metrics such as resource usage, performance indicators, and fault signals.
2. **Swarm Agents (SAs)** utilise this monitoring data to assess the overall health and performance of the application from a distributed perspective.
3. The **network of SAs** within the Swarm collaboratively analyses the monitoring information to determine whether reconfiguration is required. Reconfiguration decisions can either emerge collectively or be proposed by individual SAs and finalised through a consensus mechanism, where one SA is elected as the Lead SA for coordination.
4. Once a decision is made, the **Lead SA initiates the execution** of the appropriate reconfiguration action, applying it across the necessary components and resources.

Based on the structure of the Swarm (as shown in Figure 13), Swarmchestrator supports two primary types of reconfiguration actions. The details of these actions and how these will be handled are discussed in the following subsections.

3.4.1 Type-1 reconfigurations

This type of reconfiguration involves changes to the Swarm's resource composition, such as the following actions:

1. **Scale out resources:** This action involves provisioning additional resources to meet growing application demands. It may require adding a new instance of an existing resource type (e.g., types A, B, C, or D) to increase capacity, or introducing a new type of resource with a different configuration to enhance capability or diversify the resource pool.
2. **Scale in resources:** This involves reducing resource utilisation by terminating selected resources. This can be done by removing all instances of a particular resource type (e.g., eliminating type A) or terminating a specific instance of a resource (e.g., shutting down instance_0001 of type A) that is no longer needed.
3. **Migrate resources:** This refers to relocating a running container to a different host resource that is either more or less powerful than the current one and is not presently part of the Swarm. This step is typically taken to optimise resource utilisation or meet changing QoS requirements.

This type of reconfiguration decision will reuse the deployment process, as the key idea here is to select a new resource to meet a specific requirement. When the reconfiguration decision is taken, the lead SA will submit a request to its associated RA requesting the specific resource(s). The receiving RA will broadcast the request, and follow the same procedure discussed earlier as part of the application deployment.

3.4.2 Type-2 reconfigurations

This type of reconfiguration includes adjustments made within the existing resource set of the Swarm, such as the following actions.

1. **Scale up services without adding new resources:** This involves increasing service capacity by better utilising existing Swarm resources. It can be done by scaling up the service on the same resource, where it is currently running, to improve performance, or by deploying additional instances of the service on other existing Swarm resources to distribute the load.
2. **Scale down containers without removing resources:** This action reduces service usage without terminating the underlying infrastructure. It can involve: terminating any instance of a particular service to reduce redundancy or cost, shutting down a service instance running on a specific resource to optimise local utilisation, or removing a specific container instance, identified by its ID or label, that is no longer required.
3. **Migrate services within the swarm:** This refers to moving a running container from one resource to another within the existing Swarm. This may be done to balance load, optimise performance, or respond to localised issues.

This type of reconfiguration action will involve the lead SA to amend the Kubernetes manifest and execute the action through the Kubernetes control plane within the Swarm, without affecting the existing resources.

4. Context-aware adaptive decentralised monitoring

The reconfigurations decided by the orchestration component rely on data drawn by the application and resource monitoring. The focus of this task is the design and implementation of a decentralised, adaptive monitoring mechanism tailored to the unique challenges of managing applications deployed across the highly dynamic and geographically distributed Swarm-based Orchestration Space. We built upon the Event Management System (EMS) architecture that was researched and developed as part of the Horizon Europe NebulOUS⁷ project. T2.3 aims to extend this foundational framework to support advanced self-healing capabilities and improved resilience in environments characterised by intermittent connectivity, heterogeneous resources, and energy constraints. The monitoring mechanism developed in this task leverages federated event processing agents to ensure decentralised and fault-tolerant data propagation, enabling real-time system awareness and facilitating timely application reconfiguration decisions. Contextual information collected from the various infrastructure, networking, and application layers are used to inform the intelligent, AI-driven processes for the dynamic runtime management researched and developed in T2.4. The resulting system aims to empower Swarmchestrator's self-adaptive orchestration capabilities, ensuring robust, efficient, and scalable management of applications in the cloud continuum.

4.1 Event Monitoring System (EMS)

EMS follows a **hierarchical and decentralized approach**, designed to be fault-tolerant in dynamic computing continuum settings. Therefore, EMS agents are not passive entities waiting for server instructions but are enhanced to form autonomous **local clusters** by dynamically discovering and collaborating with their neighboring peers. These clusters operate under a distributed membership protocol that allows EMS clients to detect peer availability, withstand short-term connectivity disruptions, and recover from node or aggregator failures. Each cluster is capable of autonomously selecting a new aggregator if the current one becomes unavailable, thereby maintaining monitoring continuity without server intervention. Therefore, EMS follows a multi-layered **Distributed Complex Event Processing (DCEP)** architecture that dynamically adapts to cloud, fog, and edge infrastructure topologies. It involves Event Processing Managers (EPMs) and Event Processing Agents (EPAs) that can reconfigure their monitoring roles in real time based on resource capabilities and application deployment changes. This architecture not only ensures resilient and scalable monitoring across heterogeneous and volatile environments, but also enables fine-grained, real-time quality-of-service (QoS) feedback-critical for triggering SLO-aware application adaptations.

⁷ <https://nebulouscloud.eu/>

Figure 20: Different levels of processing (1st level – blue , 2nd level – green, 3rd level – purple)

4.1.1 State of the Art Analysis

Centralized Monitoring Frameworks

Traditional monitoring tools like Nagios⁸ and Zabbix⁹ follow a *central-server* model, collecting data via agents or probes. For example, Zabbix can use **proxies** (lightweight collectors) to distribute monitoring tasks across many locations but still relies on central aggregation. Prometheus¹⁰ typically scrapes metrics from endpoints; only recently has it offered an *agent mode* that forwards data upward. The use of Zabbix paired with Grafana for the implementation of a real-time monitoring and alert system was demonstrated by Velasco et al. [60]. As the Prometheus team notes, the emergence of tiny “edge clusters” means almost all observability data must be sent to larger “remote, bigger counterparts,”

8 <https://www.nagios.org/>

9 <https://www.zabbix.com/>

10 prometheus.io

imposing a global aggregation bottleneck. In sum, these centralized frameworks (Nagios, Zabbix, Prometheus, etc.) are proven and mature, but their **single-point-of-aggregation** design can become a bottleneck or single failure point in highly distributed cloud–fog–edge environments. Their scalability is often addressed via federated/prometheus remotes or proxies, but inherent limitations remain for very dynamic or resource-constrained deployments.

Decentralized/Federated Monitoring

To overcome central bottlenecks, some systems use *federation* or multi-master setups. For instance, Prometheus supports **federation** or Remote-Write endpoints to forward subsets of metrics to a “global” Prometheus, reducing direct cross-network scrapes. Similarly, Zabbix can deploy multiple servers or proxies in different sites that forward summaries to a main server. These approaches reduce single-point load but still require hierarchy or “global view” coordination. Overall, federated monitoring retains some central coordination, which can be a weakness for ultra-large, highly dynamic infrastructures.

Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Monitoring Architectures

Peer-to-peer monitoring solutions form a flat or hierarchical mesh of equal nodes, avoiding fixed collectors. For example, **FogMon** [61] is a P2P fog monitoring system that uses a two-tier (leader–follower) gossip overlay. Each leader aggregates local fog-node data and gossip-distributes summaries. FogMon targets Fog/IoT infrastructures, monitoring CPU/network/IoT-device metrics in a lightweight way. More recently, Colombo *et al.* [62] proposed a *self-adaptive P2P* extension of FogMon. Their system uses the MAPE-K feedback loop embedded in each peer to adjust monitoring behavior at runtime. Adaptive rules allow **dynamic sampling** and **dynamic indicator selection**: e.g., increasing/decreasing probe rates or enabling/disabling metrics based on current trends. This AdaptiveMon prototype (a FogMon extension) achieved higher data accuracy and lower network/power use under edge conditions. Other P2P examples include **SkyEye**[63], a tree-based P2P monitor for continuous metric collection and gossip-based schemes. Femminella and Reali describe a gossip-based monitoring protocol for 6G/edge networks: each node runs a light monitoring agent and exchanges status via gossip, which “increases reliability” and keeps decisions local, limiting central coordination [64]. In summary, P2P approaches (FogMon and its adaptive variants, gossip protocols, etc.) inherently tolerate churn and distribute the load. They can adapt to dynamic topologies and can implement custom peer-local intelligence, making them well suited for cloud–fog–edge environments.

CEP and Distributed CEP Frameworks

Complex-Event-Processing (CEP) is integral to modern monitoring: it detects composite events, Service Level Objectives (SLOs) or Service Level Agreement (SLA) violations from raw

metrics streams. Traditional CEP engines (like Esper¹¹ or libraries in Apache Flink¹²/Storm¹³) are often deployed centrally or on the computationally strongest nodes. Research shows moving CEP closer to edge yields gains: a testbed CEP fog architecture (using pub/sub and low-cost devices) cuts event-detection latency versus cloud-only deployment, and uses resources more efficiently [65]. For distributed CEP, specialized engines have been developed. **BoboCEP** is a fault-tolerant CEP engine designed for IoT edge: it replicates partially-completed events across multiple edge instances so that an insight is not lost if nodes fail. It can run on n devices and tolerate up to $n-1$ failures, ensuring reliable event detection at the edge [66]. Another example is EdgeCEP [67], which partitions CEP queries across a self-organized network of sensors. Overall, CEP/DCEP solutions aim to push event analysis into the fog/edge layer rather than backhaul raw data to the cloud.

Blockchain-based Monitoring Solutions

Blockchain technologies have been proposed to decentralize and secure monitoring. The **HLF-Kubed** framework [68] exemplifies this: it uses a Kubernetes (K3s) cluster of Hyperledger Fabric nodes as a tamper-proof ledger of resource measurements. HLF-Kubed is described as a “highly available framework for monitoring edge devices” that leverages distributed ledger technology. By storing metrics on a permissioned blockchain, it avoids a single point of failure and provides an immutable audit trail of usage. In practice, HLF-Kubed deploys lightweight Fabric peers on K3s-managed edge nodes, and it uses smart contracts to record and query sensor data. Its experiments report low overhead and minimal CPU/memory footprint even on constrained nodes. The trade-off is higher complexity: blockchains impose consensus and storage costs.

Self-Healing

Kubernetes inherently supports self-healing capabilities across multiple levels. It implements this by continuously reconciling the desired state of workloads. For example, the deployment controllers ensure that the required number of pods is always running; if a pod or container crashes, Kubernetes will start a new one to replace it. At the pod level, the health check and self-healing is achieved through liveness and readiness probes. The first ones can monitor the container’s status. If the state of the container detected by the probe isn’t the desired (e.g. unresponsive), the probe’s diagnostic results in “Failure”, and then Kubernetes through kubelet can terminate it and restart it or create a new one based on the restart policy. Readiness probes on the other hand, are responsible for checking whether a container can properly serve requests made to them, ensuring that only healthy and fully-initialized pods receive traffic, preventing users from encountering unavailable services. In case of failure, the system will delete the IP address of the affected pod. The self-healing capabilities of K8s also includes replica replacements in the case a pod in Deployment or StatefulSet or DaemonSet fails, as well as reattaching the persistent volume attached to it to

¹¹ <https://www.esper.tech.com/esper/>

¹² <https://flink.apache.org/>

¹³ <https://storm.apache.org/>

a new pod on a different node. In case of persistent volume failure, further recovery may be needed manually. At node level, when a physical or virtual machine fails, Kubernetes detects the issue, and automatically reschedules the affected pods to healthy nodes, minimizing service disruption due to hardware or system faults. Finally, Kubernetes also includes a deployment rollback mechanism. If a new version introduces problems, the system can automatically revert to the last stable version through ReplicaSets, preserving operational stability through [69], [70], [71].

In Swarmchestrator's project K3s is used. K3s is a CNCF-certified, lightweight Kubernetes distribution optimized for resource-constrained and edge use cases. It provides the same API and core behaviour as standard Kubernetes, so it inherently includes the same pod-level self-healing mechanisms. In practice, a K3s cluster still uses ReplicaSets, probes, and node health checks just like upstream Kubernetes, so container crashes are still detected and restarted automatically. Importantly, K3s adds its own high-availability (HA) and self-healing features. In HA mode, multiple K3s server nodes run the API and the datastore (via an etc quorum). Since the control plane is "self-hosted" on any server, losing one node does not disrupt the cluster: if a server fails, another server node automatically takes over the control-plane role without losing data or configuration. In summary, K3s retains Kubernetes' container-level healing while also simplifying the cluster control plane [70].

Of course, advancements on self-healing extend a lot more than inside the Kubernetes environment. Some important pieces of recent research that has introduced advanced self-healing mechanisms are:

Smart HPA [72] introduces a hierarchical auto-scaler combining centralized and decentralized strategies to optimize resource allocation in Kubernetes microservices. It improves scaling efficiency in resource-constrained environments by dynamically redistributing resources among services.

Mirus et al. [73] propose a behaviour tree-based framework for monitoring and mitigating application failures in distributed robotic systems using Kubernetes and ROS2. It enables reactive, stateful recovery strategies without modifying application code, enhancing resilience in complex robotics environments.

Deepak Kaul [74] introduced an AI-driven framework designed to enhance self-healing capabilities in Kubernetes clusters while optimizing energy consumption. By integrating machine learning models for predictive fault detection and real-time anomaly detection, the system can proactively identify and address potential failures, reducing downtime and manual intervention. Additionally, the framework employs energy optimization algorithms that dynamically adjust resource allocation based on workload demand, achieving improved energy efficiency and enhanced fault tolerance compared to traditional approaches.

Chaos [75] is a resilient and scalable system designed for distributed training in edge computing environments. Edge clusters often face frequent node and link changes, which can disrupt distributed training processes. Chaos addresses these challenges by

implementing multi-neighbour replication with fast shard scheduling, allowing new nodes to quickly retrieve the latest training state from nearby neighbours. It also employs a cluster monitor to track resource and topology changes, assisting in scheduler decisions, and handles scaling events through peer negotiation protocols, enabling fully self-governed autoscaling without a central administrator.

Adaptive Sampling and Filtering

Adaptive sampling and filtering techniques have emerged as critical enablers for reducing data volumes, conserving resources, and maintaining accuracy across cloud–edge and swarm-oriented infrastructures. By tailoring data collection and processing dynamically—based on system state, signal characteristics, or environmental context—these methods address the pressing need to balance fidelity with constrained bandwidth, computational capacity, and energy budgets. Below, we distill the most impactful approaches and their limitations, drawing on representative works in the field.

Adaptive sampling adjusts measurement or transmission rates in response to changing conditions, ensuring that only contextually salient data are captured at high resolution. Three prominent paradigms illustrate this balance:

The Adaptive Monitoring Service (AMS) [76] exploits statistical dependencies between variables to reduce transmission volume. By identifying a small set of regressor variables (RVs) and using cloud- or edge-based models to predict dependent variables (DVs), AMS transmits only RVs at full frequency. In smart-city deployments, this strategy achieved a 40% reduction in data flow while preserving 92% reconstruction accuracy. The principal drawback lies in environments where correlations shift unpredictably—such as during emergencies or anomalous events—necessitating frequent retraining of prediction models and inflating edge compute costs.

For Cyber-Physical Systems, leveraging the first derivative of sensor signals provides a lightweight trigger: rapid changes (e.g., sudden temperature spikes) prompt higher sampling rates, whereas quiescent periods allow lower rates [77]. Simulations indicate a 71% drop in processor utilization without sacrificing temporal precision. However, computing derivatives at high frequencies can itself introduce latency and computational overhead, limiting applicability to ultra–low-latency scenarios or highly resource-constrained devices.

By maintaining a cloud-resident time-series forecasting model that continuously predicts edge metrics, this approach [78] requests updates only when forecast confidence falls below a threshold. Applied to IoT traffic datasets, it cut transmissions by 58 % while bounding prediction errors under 12%. Yet, reliance on historical data hampers responsiveness in rapidly evolving contexts (e.g., unforeseen network disruptions or novel workloads), as the forecast model may not generalize to unseen patterns without retraining.

Collectively, these methods advance toward adaptive, resource-efficient sampling. Yet, they share two key challenges: (a) managing dynamic relationships among variables that can abruptly change—and thus invalidate learned correlations or forecast models—and (b) limiting edge-side computation so that derivative calculations or model inferences do not overwhelm constrained nodes.

Adaptive filtering techniques complement sampling by pruning or processing data locally to further minimize unnecessary transmissions. They typically focus on preserving mission-critical information (i.e., detecting anomalies or events) while discarding noise, redundancy, or data that falls within expected ranges:

In distributed sensor networks, a Kalman filter predicts the next measurement and discards any observed value that falls within an acceptable error bound [79]. This approach achieved a 33% reduction in communication overhead on Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) networks, leveraging the filter's linear complexity ($O(n)$) for scalability. Nonetheless, Kalman filters assume Gaussian noise; when noise distributions are nonstationary or heavy-tailed, performance deteriorates, necessitating manual recalibration or more robust—but costlier—filter variants.

AdaptiveMon [62] is a self-adaptive, peer-to-peer framework where lightweight rules (e.g., “if CPU > 80% then increase sampling”) modulate monitoring intensity across fog nodes. Simulations showed a 29% drop in network traffic and 18% in power consumption, with only 15% memory overhead. However, as swarm scale grows, coordinating rule sets among numerous peers becomes increasingly complex; global consistency and avoidance of oscillatory behaviors (e.g., simultaneous upscaling of all nodes) present nontrivial challenges.

The AdaM framework [80] combines both adaptive sampling and filtering on IoT devices. A dual-threshold scheme discards data within expected ranges (e.g., human body temperature $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$) while adjusting sampling frequency based on trend analysis. Real-world deployments reported 74% fewer transmissions and 71% energy savings. Yet overly aggressive thresholds risk missing gradual but critical drifts—such as slow-onset Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) failures in industrial settings—if anomalies fall just below the predefined bounds.

Although each filtering method contributes significant resource savings, two overarching limitations remain: sensitivity to noise characteristics (particularly for linear filters like Kalman), and difficulties achieving global coordination in large swarms or heterogeneous fog environments without incurring prohibitive overhead.

4.1.2 EMS in Swarmchestrator

We are adapting the technologies used in EMS to fit the swarm-based approach and enhancing its capabilities. First, we are extending it to be able to translate the Metric Model expressed in TOSCA into the CAMEL DSL used by EMS, as well as creating the necessary entities in TOSCA for monitoring as seen in section 2.3. As far as the Event monitoring system is concerned, our investigation is based on three axes. The first one is investigating self-healing capabilities of the Event Processing Managers that hasn't been previously addressed (e.g., in the NebulOuS project). The second one is investigating adaptive sampling and filtering to decrease the propagated information, thus improving the bandwidth use by the system. The third one to be investigated in the future is potential cross-EPMS

communication for applications belonging to the same organisation, hence requiring aggregation of metrics or composite metrics through their different applications.

4.1.3 Approach

In the context of this project, the Event Monitoring System is responsible for monitoring the resources and applications running through Swarmchestrate and capturing SLO violations that may occur. When such violations are detected, an event will be emitted, to be consumed by the Orchestrator, for reconfiguration to be initiated. An instance of the Event Monitoring System is going to be deployed in each Swarmchestrate universe. Each universe is responsible for each application running, is independent and consists of its own cluster with the required monitoring entities, an EPM and several EPAs, as explained in the above sections. Furthermore, in the case of inter-swarm communication, potential extensions of the EMS for cross-swarm Event Processing Manager communication will be investigated. The place of the EMS in each swarm is clearly portrayed in the figure below:

Figure 21: Integration of EMS in Swarmchestrate

Initially, at the deployment time of the application, EMS receives the forwarded TOSCA application description from the orchestrator, from where the Metric Model information is extracted. After the Metric Model is translated and analysed, the EPAs are deployed along

with the monitoring aspects that should be observed for each component. EPAs in each resource of the application possess monitoring probes that either directly capture monitoring metrics or receive the exported application-level metrics. EMS along with the EPAs comprise the Event Processing Network shown in the figure above. During runtime, EMS continuously receives metrics from the applications and their hosts, aggregates them, processes them and checks for violations (i.e., composite metrics). The detailed functionalities and components are described in the following sections. When the desired composite metrics are produced, as seen in the figure, they are propagated to the rest of the Swarmchestrator universe through pub/sub channels, called topics. There are two types of topics that are important to the other components of the system. The first ones are named after the metric needed to be monitored e.g. “metric_name”, and the second ones which refer to the SLO of the metric “metric_name_SLO”. The Orchestrator Agent as well as the Decentralised Data Management subscribe to these topics and receive real-time data. The Decentralised Data Management is going to persist the composite metrics whereas the Orchestrator Agent is going to forward the data needed by the AI agent and get notified by the SLO violation events to trigger reconfigurations.

4.1.4 Conceptual Architecture

EMS orchestrates a distributed network of agents, named, the Event Processing Network (EPN), that gathers telemetry from automatically deployed monitoring probes. Using a Complex Event Processing (CEP) engine, event patterns are extracted from the sensor data, which are then published in the EPN. A CEP engine is a software system designed to perform event processing, which involves continuously and incrementally analyzing streams of real-time event data to detect meaningful patterns (over time or event windows), relationships, or complex events and trigger immediate responses. Communication is achieved through message brokers, i.e. software systems that propagate messages using different messaging protocols. Specifically, EMS utilizes Apache ActiveMQ Artemis¹⁴, a high-performance open-source solution as a message broker, with support for the Advanced Message Queueing Protocol (AMQP).

Leveraging sophisticated complex event processing, these raw data streams are filtered and analyzed to identify SLOs, while conserving communication bandwidth. To build this monitoring mesh correctly, EMS must understand the application’s Quality of Service (QoS) demands. To achieve this, EMS ingests declarative specifications defined by the user within Swarmchestrator through the TOSCA model, which the EMS transforms into a Metric Model. The Metric Model drives EMS in determining exactly which measurements to collect and how to process them, based on each component’s SLOs. Architecturally, EMS splits into a central server (the Event Processing Manager, EPM) and lightweight agents (Event Processing Agents, EPAs) that deploy alongside each application component across cloud, fog, and edge nodes.

¹⁴ <https://activemq.apache.org/components/artemis/>

Core EMS Responsibilities

- **Model Analysis:** The EPM decodes the Swarmchestrator Metric Model to extract required metrics and compile corresponding CEP rules.
- **Agent Configuration:** Tailoring each EPA's sensor set and CEP rulebook according to the specific workloads and placement decisions generated by the Swarmchestrator Optimiser.

EPM Internal Modules

- **TOSCA translator:** Parses TOSCA model specifications and converts to a Metric Model that EMS can utilize
- **Metric Model Translator:** Parses the Metric Model into a multi-root DAG, generates Esper (EPL) rules, and adapts to changes in the DSL or storage backend. It includes:
 - **Validator:** Ensures the model's syntax and references (e.g., sensors, raw metrics) are complete and correct.
 - **Persistence:** Archives the original model and all derivative artifacts (DAGs, EPL scripts) in the file system.
- **Configurator:** Assembles EPA settings-metrics to capture, CEP rules, event propagation and clustering parameters, and credentials.
- **Baguette Server:** Manages the live topology of the EPN and comprises:
 - **Node Registry:** An SSH endpoint for EPAs to fetch configurations and report their cluster roles.
 - **Topology Coordinator:** Assigns EPA groupings and pushes tailored configurations based on the translated model.
 - **Control Service:** Oversees all EPM workflows, interfaces with the Swarmchestrator Control Plane, and offers management and debugging endpoints.
- **Broker-CEP Service:** Bundles a message broker and Esper engine to route and evaluate events against active CEP rules.
- **Local Topology Manager:** Within a federated set of EPMs, this component tracks peer managers and elects a primary aggregator. If a failure occurs, standby nodes rerun the election and reconfigure EPAs to use the new leader.
- **Plugin Framework:** A pluggable API that lets developers extend EPM capabilities (e.g., interfacing with AMQP brokers, or dynamically reloading models).
- **Subscriptions Advisor:** Calculates which event streams (raw, composite, predicted) other Swarmchestrator components must subscribe to, based on the metric model and utility functions.
- **Configuration Manager & Web Console:** Caches EPA configuration for installers and provides a dashboard for monitoring the local event broker's health and activity.

Figure 22: Architecture of Event Processing Manager

EPA Architecture

Each EPA consists of:

- **Baguette Client:** A liaison to the EPM, including:
 - **SSH Client:** Securely retrieves instructions from the Baguette Server.
 - **Command Executor:** Launches and configures the local Broker-CEP service per received directives.
- **Broker-CEP Service:** Hosts the local Esper CEP engine alongside an embedded message broker (e.g., ActiveMQ), publishing and consuming events among EPAs.
- **Local Topology Manager:** Forms a resilient, dynamic cluster of EPAs using Atomix¹², electing local aggregators and updating CEP settings when leadership or EPM endpoints change.
- **Plugin Framework:** Allows EPA extensions, such as the bundled Netdata Collector for telemetry retrieval and a Health Checker that probes peer EPAs' brokers for liveness.

Figure 23: Architecture of Event Processing Agent

Together, the EPM and EPAs create a scalable, QoS-driven monitoring system – SWARMCHESTRATE’s EMS – capable of managing the heterogeneity and dynamism of cloud-continuum environments

4.1.5 EMS in Swarm-based Orchestration Space

Tosca to Metric Model translator

The introduction of the TOSCA to Nebulous Metric Model Translator augments EMS with a new front-end capable of consuming TOSCA-style topology descriptions and automatically generating the Metric Model that EPM has traditionally required. This translator enables the users to specify their application’s monitoring scopes, components, raw and composite metrics, and SLO constraints in a widely adopted TOSCA format - thus broadening EMS’s interoperability with existing cloud-orchestration toolchains.

At runtime, the translator performs the following steps:

Model Transformation

- **Metadata Enrichment:** Automatically stamps the CAMEL output with file-level metadata (e.g. source filename).
- **Node Classification:** Iterates over each `node_types` entry, distinguishing those tagged as `MonitoringScope` (becoming CAMEL “scopes”) from ordinary components.
 - **Capability Extraction:** For each node it invokes `processNodeCapabilities` to collate lists of:
 - Raw Metrics (collector type, configuration, frequency, “busy-status” flags)
 - Composite Metrics (formulae, sliding windows, post-processing criteria)
 - SLO Requirements (name, constraint expressions)

By slotting this translator in front of the EPM pipeline, EMS now natively supports TOSCA descriptions. The translator’s modular design (with clear separation between parsing, capability processing, and YAML generation) ensures that future extensions-such as additional metric types or alternative input DSLs can be accommodated with minimal disruption to the core EMS architecture (section 4.1.5).

Deployment of Nodes

The workflow for deploying the necessary Event Processing Agents (EPAs) to enable monitoring of an application (and subsequently forming a responsive event processing network) is triggered by the orchestrator. When an application arrives, any application specific configuration (e.g. metric model, etc) is dynamically compiled, and is then passed to the orchestrator, which will take care of the automated deployment of the EPAs on the

dynamic resources that are selected for this submitted application. As each EPA instance comes online, it references the configmap to establish a connection with the EPM service (also referred to as the Baguette server) and announces its presence.

Guided by EPM's instructions, each EPA configures its monitoring tools – activating probes and any required telemetry collectors like Prometheus. The agents then deploy EPL rules to support the aggregation and processing of complex event streams, and join an EPN (Event Processing Network) cluster. Within each cluster, agents autonomously select a local aggregator node, adjust EPL rules accordingly, and report this back to the EPM. This completes the setup, enabling real-time monitoring of infrastructure, application metrics, and data streams to detect any Service Level Objective (SLO) violations that might require system adaptation.

4.2 Example of application and infrastructure level metrics

During the development process of the Swarmchestrator project, the monitoring team has been in contact with the rest of the working groups to assure the best cooperation and integration with them. We have been working closely with the Demonstrator's team for which we created a demo to demonstrate exactly how they can integrate with the Event Monitoring System. The first demo was provided through the deployment of EMS on docker containers adjusting all parameters needed. A first version of TOSCA was used and synthetic application-level metrics were created as well for the purpose of the demonstration.

As mentioned before, metrics are separated into two categories: infrastructure level metrics and application-level metrics. The first ones are related to the metrics of the resources on which the applications are running, like CPU usage, RAM usage etc. The second ones are application-specific, and need to be exported by the application owner, e.g. metrics from sensors, response time etc. For the monitoring of the infrastructure-level metrics of their applications Netdata is utilised and can cover a huge spectrum of metrics. For the application level metrics a python script was developed as a demo to help demonstrators export metrics by integrating it into their application. For this particular script prometheus_client library was used to export the metrics in a predefined port as well as a decorator for the metric. Below is an example of the definition of the particular metrics in TOSCA as well as the example script for application-level metrics exporting:

```
from prometheus_client import start_http_server, Counter, Summary
import random
import time

# Port of Prometheus endpoint
PORT = 9000

# Create a metric to count requests made
REQUEST_COUNT = Counter('request_count', 'Number of requests')

# Create a metric to track time spent and requests made.
REQUEST_TIME = Summary('request_processing_seconds', 'Time spent processing request')

# Decorate function with metric.
@REQUEST_TIME.time()
def process_request(t):
    """A dummy function that takes some time."""
    time.sleep(t)
    REQUEST_COUNT.inc()

if __name__ == '__main__':
    # Start up the server to expose the metrics.
    start_http_server(PORT)
    print(f'Exposing Prometheus metrics at port: {PORT}')
    # Generate some requests.
    while True:
        process_request(5 + 5 * random.random())
```

Figure 24: Sample code snippet that publishes raw metrics using the Prometheus API

```

1  tosca_definitions_version: tosca_2_0
2
3  imports:
4  - profiles/eu.swarmchestrate/ems/0.1/profile.yaml
5  - profiles/eu.swarmchestrate/micado/0.1/profile.yaml
6
7  service_template:
8  node_templates:
9  COMPONENT_NAME: # e.g. webserver, database, etc.
10 type: MonitoringComponent
11 capabilities:
12 metrics:
13   properties:
14     raw:
15     - name: cpu_util_instance
16       sensor: "Netdata"
17       config:
18         scope_contexts: system.cpu
19         results-aggregation: SUM
20         collection_frequency: "30 sec"
21         collection_output: "all"
22     - name: response_time
23       sensor: "Prometheus"
24       config:
25         metric: "request_processing_seconds_sum"
26         port: 9000
27         endpoint: "/"
28         delay: 0
29         collection_frequency: "30 sec"
30         collection_output: "all"
31     composite:
32     - name: mean_cpu_util_prct
33       formula: mean( cpu_util_instance )
34       collection_frequency: "30 sec"
35       collection_output: "all"
36       window_type: "sliding"
37       window_size: "5 min"
38       grouping: "per_zone" # e.g. PER_HOST/PER_ZONE/PER_REGION/CROSS-SWARMS
39
40 requirements: # defined when a violation occurs . e.g. raise event when cpu_util_instance > 80
41 properties:
42   slo:
43   - name: cpu_slo
44     metric: "mean_cpu_util_prct"
45     operator: ">" # e.g. >, <, >=, <=, ==
46     threshold: "80"

```

Figure 25: Sample of an older version of TOSCA metric model used for the demonstration of EMS

4.3 Summary

Over this first project period we worked towards adapting and extending the Event Monitoring System (EMS) in alignment with the requirements identified during the Swarmchestrate analysis phase. The initial focus has been on the TOSCA-based metric model, as outlined in the previous section (2.3). This model has undergone significant adaptation and evolution during the period from M06 to M18. In parallel with these adaptations, efforts have also been directed towards enhancing the Translator component to ensure that it consistently maps newly introduced entities to the artefacts required by the EMS. Both developments have progressed concurrently, in close collaboration and continuous communication with the pilot demonstrator teams.

As previously mentioned, a demonstrator version of the EMS has been deployed using Docker, showcasing the monitoring of infrastructure-level metrics and the collection of application-level metrics. Supporting scripts have been developed to illustrate how metrics can be exported, and guidance has been provided for defining the metric model. Experimental deployments on K3s are also underway.

In addition, research has been conducted into cutting-edge technologies and methodologies for adaptive sampling and filtering. The team has engaged in state-of-the-art analysis and internal sessions to evaluate potential enhancements and define the next steps. A similar approach has been applied regarding the investigation of self-healing mechanisms, aiming to identify current limitations of the EMS and outline directions for future development.

Finally, the team is in the process of finalizing the integration details between the Monitoring System and the Decentralized Knowledge Base.

4.4 Next steps for EMS

Regarding adaptive sampling and filtering, we will investigate implementing techniques based on the first derivative of key metrics, such as loss, accuracy, or resource usage. By monitoring the rate of change (i.e., the first derivative) of these metrics over time, we aim to dynamically adjust the sampling frequency—sampling more frequently during periods of rapid change or instability and reducing frequency during plateaus or convergence. This approach has been implemented in cyber-physical systems, but not for monitoring cloud-to-edge applications, and could improve both computational efficiency and responsiveness, enabling the system to focus on resources where they are most needed without sacrificing observability or control.

When it comes to self-healing, even though kubernetes platform covers most of infrastructure-related healing actions needed, we will investigate how restarted pods that host EPAs should rejoin the EPN network, when failures are detected. Apart from that we are going to investigate actions needed to be taken when an EPM failure occurs and how to smoothly restore EMS's functionality.

5. Optimising energy efficiency and ecological sustainability of applications

The rapid expansion of cloud-edge infrastructures has thrust energy efficiency into the focus of research. As data centres and edge nodes shoulder increasingly complex workloads, their electricity consumption—and the associated costs and environmental impact—continue to rise [81]. Improving the energy performance of cloud-edge systems therefore promises lower operating expenses, a smaller carbon footprint and more sustainable digital services. Realising these benefits, however, demands solutions that balance resource utilisation, system performance and power draw. In this context, machine learning (ML) and artificial

intelligence (AI) have become pivotal research avenues for optimising energy usage across distributed cloud-edge environments.

Existing literature surveys discuss how ML and AI techniques can enhance energy efficiency, examining factors such as throughput, trust in nationwide and provider-specific infrastructures, cross-border applications, virtual-machine (VM) placement, run-time VM migration and cost. Yet no prior review has thoroughly addressed two equally crucial dimensions of resource allocation:

- Urgency, and
- Environmental rating of resources

These factors play a decisive role in scheduling decisions, and overlooking them leaves a significant gap in the current literature.

5.1 State-of-the-Art

To capture the current research landscape, we conducted a systematic literature review (SLR). The SLR method offers an explicit, reproducible protocol that both minimises bias and guards against information overload. We began with a comprehensive search of four premier scholarly databases—IEEE Xplore, the ACM Digital Library, Web of Science and Scopus—yielding 7 602 records. After eliminating duplicates, applying a publication-date filter and performing an initial relevance screen, the dataset was narrowed to 86 articles. A subsequent, detailed appraisal against pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria further distilled the corpus to 73 studies, which we deemed the most pertinent and influential. Drawing solely from high-quality sources underpins the robustness of our review.

5.1.1 Overall AI Trends for Achieving Energy Efficiency

A clear set of patterns emerges from the literature on machine-learning-driven energy optimisation in cloud-edge environments. Two reinforcement-learning (RL) families dominate:

- *Deep reinforcement learning (DRL)* – cited in 22 studies – is the most prevalent, underpinning resource optimisation, task scheduling and workload offloading.
- *Classical RL* (12 studies) and *multi-agent RL (MARL)* (4 studies) likewise boost performance and balance dynamic workloads, enabling adaptive, energy-aware resource allocation.

Beyond RL, researchers frequently employ:

- *Neural-network and deep-learning models (e.g. LSTM, RNN)* – 12 studies – for workload-pattern recognition and energy-consumption prediction.
- *Federated learning* – 4 studies – to train models collaboratively across edge devices, saving energy while preserving data privacy.

Hybrid approaches that blend ML with heuristic or meta-heuristic techniques—such as genetic algorithms (GA) and particle-swarm optimisation—are gaining traction for complex optimisation tasks. An illustrative example is the combination of RL with GA to enhance virtual-machine migration and resource allocation.

Emerging methods, including *graph convolutional neural networks (GCNNs)* and *transfer learning*, appear less often, signalling promising but still nascent avenues for future work.

5.1.2 Findings Related to Balancing Urgency and Energy Efficiency

Recent studies report notable progress in reconciling fast task execution with frugal power use in cloud-edge systems. Most adopt reinforcement-learning (RL) techniques—especially deep RL (DRL)—to derive policies that schedule workloads and migrate virtual machines (VMs) in real time while respecting tight energy budgets. For example, Rahman and Pichandi fuse adaptive RL with ant-colony optimisation to prioritise urgent requests yet still perform energy-aware VM migrations [82]. Zeng et al. harness RL for collaborative offloading in multi-user edge environments, shaving latency [83], whereas Hoang et al. exploit DRL to fine-tune resource allocation, simultaneously reducing delay and power draw [83], [84]. Extending this line of work, Tong et al. introduce a multi-agent DRL framework that dynamically elevates time-critical workloads [83], [84], [85].

Multi-agent RL (MARL) schemes excel in highly variable settings. Asghari et al. deploy MARL agents across cloud and edge layers to optimise resources for time-sensitive workflows, achieving lower latency and balanced utilisation without breaching energy targets [86]. In fog-computing contexts, Shahidani et al. develop RL-driven load-balancers that keep urgent tasks close to the data source, thus minimising back-haul overhead and response time .

Across the literature, one theme recurs: the delicate trade-off between immediate responsiveness and long-term energy efficiency. DRL models generally embed reward functions that penalise both latency and excessive power use, enabling them to pre-position resources for anticipated surges instead of resorting to energy-intensive reactive measures. Nevertheless, scalability remains a challenge—training and maintaining RL models in large, multi-tenant deployments can be computationally expensive and may erode some of the expected energy savings.

5.1.3 Findings Related to Environmental Ratings for Optimization

A growing body of work now factors environmental ratings—metrics such as carbon intensity and renewable-energy penetration—into resource-allocation decisions for cloud-edge systems. Several studies weave these ratings directly into machine-learning (ML) models to strike a balance between performance, cost and ecological impact. Li et al., for instance, propose a multi-objective optimiser that jointly minimises energy use and carbon emissions [87], while Wang et al. present energy-aware distributed-learning techniques for IoT edges to foster greener operation [88].

Carbon-aware schedulers feature prominently. Shahidani et al. and Rahman and Pichandi show that prioritising workloads for data centres powered by renewables—or regions with lower grid carbon intensity—cuts emissions without sacrificing service quality [82], [89]. In many cases, federated-learning frameworks underpin these solutions, enabling collaborative model training across dispersed devices while curbing the carbon footprint of that very training process.

Some researchers go a step further by incorporating real-time energy-market signals. Asghari et al. combine predictive analytics with live electricity-mix data, deferring energy-hungry tasks until renewable generation peaks—thereby delivering simultaneous cost and emission savings [86].

Despite encouraging results, two hurdles persist. First, the field lacks universally accepted metrics for environmental ratings, complicating cross-study comparisons. Second, real-time energy data are not always available or granular enough, and linking them to dynamic ML models introduces computational overhead that can erode the very energy gains these methods promise.

5.1.4 Limitations

Despite encouraging results, current solutions still face barriers that limit their adoption and impact at scale.

- *Scalability constraints* – Techniques such as deep reinforcement learning (DRL) and multi-agent systems perform well in small testbeds but impose heavy computational overhead when deployed across extensive cloud-edge fabrics. Asghari et al. note that single-agent models struggle once workflows involve large task graphs, signalling the need for lighter, more scalable multi-agent frameworks [86].
- *Limited adaptability to workload bursts* – Many proposals rely on quasi-static scheduling rules. When workload intensity shifts sharply, these schedulers cannot react fast enough, leading to latency spikes and wasted energy. Rahman and Pichandi document such inefficiencies and call for resource managers that can re-optimize in real time [82].
- *Opacity and training overhead of ML models* – The black-box nature of advanced learning methods hampers operational trust. Shahidani et al. underline the difficulty of interpreting DRL decisions in production settings [89]. Moreover, training DRL agents demands substantial compute and power, partially eroding the energy gains they aim to deliver [82], [86].
- *Under-utilisation of environmental ratings* – While carbon-aware schedulers are emerging, few studies embed real-time environmental metrics directly into learning objectives and decision policies. Integrating such ratings throughout the resource-management stack remains an open research frontier.

Overcoming these limitations will require lightweight distributed learning architectures, sub-second control loops, explainable decision-making, and rich data pipelines that stream live environmental signals into optimisation algorithms.

5.1.5 Recommendation for Research Conducted within Swarmchestrator

Swarmchestrator work could prioritise scalable multi-agent reinforcement-learning (MARL) frameworks that operate effectively in large, geographically dispersed settings.

A second promising direction is the tight coupling of environmental metrics—such as real-time carbon-intensity data and renewable-energy availability—into task-scheduling objectives. Carbon-aware orchestration could show how environmentally informed policies simultaneously meet workload deadlines and cut greenhouse-gas emissions.

Taken together, these avenues highlight the need for interdisciplinary research that integrates urgency, energy efficiency and sustainability.

5.2 The Swarmchestrator approach

5.2.1. Design of the energy optimization framework

Based on the outcome of the systematic literature research in the previous section, it can be stated that a sustainable, intelligence-driven resource-allocation framework must achieve three goals in concert: (1) minimise energy consumption; (2) honour Quality-of-Service (QoS) requirements and service-level agreements (SLAs); and (3) preserve load balance and scalability across a distributed infrastructure.

In order to achieve that, our contribution is distinguished by an integrated design that unifies objectives in a single, coherent framework. In particular, the design allows to:

- *Deploy multiple autonomous agents* trained via multi-agent deep reinforcement learning (MA-DRL);
- *Operate in a federated, decentralised environment*, preserving provider autonomy and eliminating single points of failure;
- *Elevate energy optimisation* from a secondary constraint to a parameterized constraint;
- *Propose full application placement*, covering persistent services and APIs;
- *Support agent-level coordination*, enabling dynamic resource sharing and decentralised decision-making.

As the basis for the design, the following research papers have been considered as the foundation for the work.

No	Paper	Multi-agent DRL	Federated Orchestration	Energy-aware Optimization	Type of Placement Targeted	Coordination Mode
1	Zhang et al. (2024)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Caching	Decentralized
2	Wu & Guan (2024)	Yes	No	Partial	Tasks	Decentralized
3	Goudarzi et al. (2024) - μ -DDRL	Yes	Partial	Yes	Tasks/Services	Decentralized
4	Siyadatzaheh et al. (2023) - Relief	Yes	No	Yes	Tasks	Decentralized
5	Liu et al. (2023) - Async DRL for Vehicular Edge	Yes	Partial	Yes	Tasks	Decentralized
6	Nkenyereye et al. (2023)	Yes	Partial	Yes	Container Inference	Decentralized
7	Wang et al. (2021) - Microservice Coordination via RL	Yes	Partial	Yes	Microservices	Decentralized
8	He et al. (2020) - QoE-Aware Offloading via DRL	Yes	Partial	Yes	Tasks	Decentralized
9	Wang et al. (2020) - Federated DRL for IoT Edge Caching	Yes	Yes	Yes	Caching	Decentralized
10	Lei et al. (2022) - Partial Federated DRL for Edge Caching	Yes	Partial	Yes	Caching	Decentralized
11	Xu et al. (2021) - MECC: DRL-based Collaborative Caching	Yes	Partial	Yes	Caching	Decentralized
12	Sun et al. (2023) - FDRL for RecSys Edge Caching	Yes	Yes	Yes	Caching	Decentralized

Table 2: Relevant AI-based, energy-considering, resource allocation research in cloud-edge computing (The citations to the 12 research papers are: [90], [91], [92], [93], [94], [95], [88], [96], [97], [98], [99], [100]).

5.2.2 Input and output data

The input data considered for the analysis comes from the application requirements and from the resources available.

Each capacity is described by:

- Capacity provider
- Instance type
- Number of CPUs
- CPU architecture
- Memory
- Storage
- Network bandwidth
- Network connectivity type
- Operating system
- Geographic location
- Battery level
- **Energy consumption**
- **Energy type**
- **Energy supply type**
- Price
- Trust rating level of resource
- Security level

The requirements of an application are described by:

- Number of components comprising the application
- Interconnection structure of components
- Maximum cost for all capacities consumed
- For each component:
 - Specification of minimum capacity,
 - QoS specification (Response time, requests per second, operations per second, IO throughput, network throughput, network delay, network jitter, database writes) and
 - **Energy condition (importance of consumption, energy reliability, energy budget)**
 - Urgency of component

The output is an allocation of each component to a specific capacity, specified as:

- Component ↔ Capacity

Based on this parameter, a solution is envisioned that will be implemented in Swarmchestrator.

6. Conclusions

Work Package 2 has successfully established the core architectural designs and foundational mechanisms for Swarmchestrator's vision of a decentralised, self-adaptive orchestration paradigm. This initial iteration focused on several key areas, yielding significant progress. We have defined context-aware semantics by extending the TOSCA standard to create a rich descriptive framework for both Cloud-to-Edge applications and available resource capacities. This includes a detailed metric model for the monitoring system, specifying new node types, capabilities, and data structures necessary to capture Quality of Service requirements and constraints.

The design of the application orchestration system introduces a novel, swarm-based approach that includes both the deployment and runtime phases in great depth. The deployment process, involving a decentralised collection of resource offers, QoS-aware selection, and the phased setup of a resilient swarm, has been thoroughly detailed. Run-time management is analysed and the different types of reconfigurations introduced are explained. The orchestration system is complemented by a comprehensive design for the adaptive and decentralised monitoring system, building upon the established Event Management System (EMS) to ensure fault-tolerant data propagation and real-time system awareness crucial for triggering reconfigurations. Finally, our systematic review of AI-driven

techniques has introduced the design of a novel framework for optimising energy efficiency, which uniquely considers urgency and environmental ratings as primary factors in resource allocation.

Future work will proceed on several promising fronts based on the foundations laid in this deliverable. The next iteration will focus on refining the systems and extending them accordingly. For the application deployment, the implementation of key programming libraries are completed and the next step is their integration to build the first complete prototype as part of the WP5, started from July 2025. On the runtime management part, the development of swarm agent is started, and the next step will be on the integration of monitoring system, AI and the implementation of the execution of reconfiguration actions. For the monitoring framework, advanced adaptive sampling and filtering techniques will be investigated and implemented, based on the rate of change of key metrics, to improve computational efficiency and system responsiveness and also develop robust self-healing mechanisms to address scenarios of monitoring agent failures. For energy optimization, the insights gained from research will be applied to implement the multi-agent deep reinforcement learning framework, enabling dynamic, energy-aware orchestration that balances performance with sustainability objectives.

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